

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results

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1 INTRODUCTION

Atmogeochemical monitoring belongs to the group of basic monitoring methods used for all terrestrial carbon dioxide storage sites (e.g. Payre et al., 2015). The atmogeochemical monitoring was ranked at “strongly recommended” in R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3 (Kolejka et al., 2021), which provides a detailed assessment of applicability of various monitoring methods and techniques including the recommended set of the most suitable methods for the Zar-3 site.

Detailed baseline soil gas monitoring above the Zar-3 oil & gas field was performed to determine potential soil gas anomalies, soil gas distribution and to improve the knowledge of the seal efficiency. The results are presented mainly as areal soil gas distribution maps of individual gases and continuous CO₂ content in soil gas in time plot. The maps prepared prior to the CO₂ storage will serve as a background for the future monitoring measurements during and after the true CO₂ storage making it possible to identify newly formed anomalies, if any.

The experience learned during the baseline soil gas monitoring serve as a basis for the main result V5 Site monitoring plan prepared in Task 7.5.

2 CHARACTERIZATION OF THE AREA

Detailed information regarding the area of interest are presented in R1.2 Report on pedology, geology, geomorphology, climatology, conflict of interest and nature protection (Janderková et al., 2022). This chapter briefly summarizes the Zar-3 area of interest from the (1) land use and (2) pedology point of view, which are by far the most important for the soil gas monitoring.

2.1 Land use

Most of the land is used for the agricultural purposes (Fig. 2-1). The agricultural area comprises predominantly arable land and smaller areas of vineyards. Orchards and gardens are located on more slope areas to the north. Northernmost part of the area is composed of tracts of forests known as Ždánický les Highland. Three settlements are located in the area: Uhřice (W, 750 inhabitants), Žarošice (S, 1 110 inhabitants) and Archlebov (E, 871 inhabitants). The simplified land use map presented in Fig. 2-1 is based on geographic data of the Czech Republic (ZABAGED[®]) and divides the area of interest into 3 main categories of (1) fields, (2) forests and (3) settled area.

Fig. 2-1: Simplified land use map of the Zar-3 area with the land use details in the monitoring points (see Chapter 3 of this report).

2.2 Pedology

The area of interest is typically built by Chernosols (CEm, CEx), Fluvisols (FLqc), Retisols (LUm, LUg) and Luvisols (HNm, HNg; Němeček and Tomášek, 1983). The majority of the land utilized for agriculture is covered by Chernosols (černožem, CE), which are relict soils formed in a drier, more continental climate beneath predominantly grassland, steppe and forest-steppe vegetation. The Fluvisols (fluvizem, FL) represents genetically very young soils formed from recent deposits, in the alluvium of watercourses. Same as the Chernosols, the fertile Fluvisols are mostly used in agriculture. The Resisols (luvizem, LU) are dominant soil type for forests and groves of the Ždánický les Highland located in the southern part of the area. The Luvisols (hnědozemě, HN) form a more or less continuous belt along the foot of the slopes of the Ždánický les Highland, between the area with predominantly occurring Retisols and the Chernozem area.

The soil map presented in Fig. 2-2 is based on geoscientific maps of the CGS (<https://mapy.geology.cz/pudy/>) and comprises Czech taxonomic soil classification system of Němeček et al. (2011) and World Reference Base for Soil Resources (IUSS Working Group WRB 2015).

Fig. 2-2: Soil map of the Zar-3 area. Polygons: red = area of interest; blue = protected field area; yellow = Zar-3 oil & gas field; green = production licences.

3 MONITORING CAMPAIGNS AND GRID

Both periodical and continuous soil gas monitoring was performed. The periodical monitoring campaigns were based on 95 monitoring points (Fig. 3-1). To cover the different seasons of the year, the periodical monitoring took place 3 times a year from spring 2021 to summer-autumn 2023. Following campaigns were performed: (1) spring 2021, (2) summer-autumn 2021, (3) winter 2021-2022, (4) spring 2022, (5) summer-autumn 2022, (6) winter 2022-2023, (7) spring 2023 and (8) summer-autumn 2023. Data measured in individual campaigns are listed in the 8 attachments of this report. The monitoring campaigns timing was selected with respect to the agricultural activities such as ploughing and crop harvesting.

For the continuous monitoring, 5 monitoring points from the periodical monitoring grid (Fig. 3-1) were selected. The continuous monitoring was performed from June 2021 to October 2023.

3.1 Monitoring grid

The monitoring grid for periodical monitoring consists of 95 monitoring points: 68 monitoring points (labelled 1 – 68) were chosen directly in the Zar-3 oil & gas field protected area with a regular distance of 150 m between the points. Additional 27 monitoring points (labelled 101 – 127) were selected in the adjacent area (Fig. 3-1).

Fig. 3-1: Soil gas monitoring grid composed of 68 + 27 monitoring points for periodical monitoring. Position of 5 permanent probes for continuous monitoring included.

Most of the monitoring points (67) represent cultivated agricultural fields used mainly for growing wheat, corn, sunflower or oilfield rape (see Tab. 3-1 and/or the attachments in this report). The additional monitoring points represent both mown and unmown grasslands (20) and groves or forests (8). For the continuous monitoring, 5 points (29, 102, 106, 120 and 123) were selected: 1 in the centre of the Zar-3 oil & gas field protected area, 4 at each of the cardinal points (Fig. 3-1). The land use characteristics and coordinates (in Gauss-Krüger S42 format) of all monitoring points are listed in Tab. 3-1 and Tab. 3-2.

Tab. 3-1: Land use characteristics of the monitoring points

Both monitoring grids				Grid in the Zar-3 protected area				Grid in the Zar-3 adjacent area			
Field	Grass	Grove	Total	Field	Grass	Grove	Total	Field	Grass	Grove	Total
67	20	8	95	59	5	4	68	8	15	4	27

Tab. 3-2: Coordinates (S42 format labelled as Gauss-Krüger - GK) and land use of the monitoring points

Point	Land use	X (GK)	Y (GK)	Z (m)	Point	Land use	X (GK)	Y (GK)	Z (m)
Grid in the Zar-3 protected area					49	Field	3644676	5436797	276.06
1	Field	3643912	5437735	228.34	50	Field	3644779	5436905	275.87
2	Field	3644016	5437843	247.51	51	Field	3644883	5437014	278.90
3	Field	3643917	5437523	229.16	52	Field	3644987	5437122	283.66
4	Field	3644021	5437631	238.78	53	Field	3645090	5437230	285.56
5	Field	3644124	5437740	250.91	54	Field	3644680	5436585	262.56

6	Field	3644228	5437848	256.79
7	Field	3643922	5437311	217.32
8	Field	3644025	5437419	232.10
9	Field	3644129	5437527	241.39
10	Field	3644233	5437636	243.30
11	Field	3644336	5437744	242.52
12	Field	3644440	5437853	241.34
13	Field	3644030	5437207	217.25
14	Grass	3644134	5437315	223.83
15	Field	3644237	5437424	228.69
16	Field	3644341	5437532	229.60
17	Field	3644445	5437641	228.14
18	Field	3644548	5437749	228.92
19	Grass	3644035	5436995	215.68
20	Field	3644138	5437103	217.33
21	Grass	3644242	5437212	218.97
22	Field	3644346	5437320	220.62
23	Field	3644449	5437428	223.07
24	Field	3644553	5437537	230.26
25	Field	3644657	5437645	231.22
26	Field	3644143	5436891	229.34
27	Field	3644247	5437000	237.21
28	Grove	3644350	5437108	230.07
29	Field	3644454	5437216	224.42
30	Field	3644558	5437325	231.38
31	Field	3644662	5437433	246.33
32	Field	3644765	5437542	256.38
33	Field	3644251	5436788	249.54
34	Field	3644355	5436896	250.35
35	Field	3644459	5437004	249.74
36	Field	3644563	5437113	249.15
37	Field	3644666	5437221	246.16
38	Grove	3644770	5437329	249.38
39	Grove	3644874	5437438	272.27
40	Field	3644360	5436684	262.66
41	Field	3644464	5436792	266.81
42	Field	3644567	5436901	265.68
43	Field	3644671	5437009	267.94
44	Grove	3644775	5437117	272.94
45	Grass	3644878	5437226	285.76
46	Field	3644982	5437334	285.78
47	Field	3644468	5436580	256.14
48	Field	3644572	5436689	271.13
55	Field	3644784	5436693	268.80
56	Grass	3644888	5436802	266.16
57	Field	3644991	5436910	267.95
58	Field	3645095	5437018	274.32
59	Field	3645199	5437127	282.04
60	Field	3644789	5436481	251.29
61	Field	3644892	5436590	256.77
62	Field	3644996	5436698	252.43
63	Field	3645100	5436806	260.89
64	Field	3645203	5436915	268.06
65	Field	3644897	5436377	253.21
66	Field	3645001	5436486	246.72
67	Field	3645104	5436594	250.63
68	Field	3645208	5436703	241.74
Grid in the Zar-3 adjacent area				
101	Grass	3642198	5436638	232.13
102	Grass	3642868	5436061	210.47
103	Field	3643595	5435370	200.19
104	Field	3644185	5435115	243.93
105	Grass	3644401	5435619	210.78
106	Field	3644813	5435833	224.49
107	Field	3643624	5436219	226.39
108	Grass	3643026	5436788	272.79
109	Grass	3642836	5437410	267.16
110	Grass	3643516	5438073	278.29
111	Grass	3643359	5437476	222.73
112	Grass	3643678	5436854	218.19
113	Grass	3643950	5436500	214.33
114	Grove	3644410	5436295	230.83
115	Grass	3645322	5436414	235.06
116	Grass	3645888	5436681	269.90
117	Field	3645750	5437280	296.44
118	Field	3645202	5437832	247.89
119	Grove	3644630	5439211	364.91
120	Field	3644227	5438297	277.73
121	Grass	3646712	5437196	257.59
122	Grove	3646100	5438031	249.38
123	Grass	3645706	5438469	263.87
124	Grass	3645392	5438868	278.81
125	Grove	3645618	5439478	385.45
126	Grass	3646507	5438833	342.56
127	Field	3647103	5438187	277.95

4 METHODOLOGY

The main aim of the atmo-geochemical monitoring was to characterize the soil gas geochemistry above the Zar-3 oil & gas field and to determine the baseline pattern with the spatial variations.

The soil gas monitoring consisted of following key steps:

- Periodical field measurements 3 times a year in a grid of 95 monitoring points

- Continuous monitoring of CO₂ in soil gas at 5 monitoring points
- Cross check gas sample collection, their chromatographic lab analyses and based on that the final data correction
- Spatial analysis of the measured data using 2D contour mapping software
- Time series analysis of the continuous measurement data.

As the methane concentration in soil gas was negligible, no methane gas flux measurement and calculation were performed in this project.

4.1 Periodical monitoring

Periodical soil gas monitoring (Fig. 4-1) was performed using a portable Ecoprobe-5TM instrument (RS Dynamics) with 4 infra-red detectors with independent channels for selective analyses of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), total petroleum (TP = CH₄ to C₄H₁₀) and oxygen (O₂). The range and detection limits of the infra-red detectors are in Tab. 4-1.

Fig. 4-1: Field soil gas measurement above the Zar-3 oil & gas field (left and middle), Ecoprobe 5TM portable instrument (right, source: RS Dynamics).

The soil gas composition was measured in each of 95 monitoring points at depth interval of 10-80 cm in holes drilled by a hand-drill prior to the measurement. The sampling under-pressure was used to estimate the soil permeability in situ.

In each of 8 monitoring campaigns, up to 10 gas samples were collected using manual pump and Tedlar bags or 40 ml EPA vials. The samples were analysed in laboratory by gas chromatography (GC-TCD-FID). Laboratory results were used for calibration of the entire set of field measurements. Those data are not included in this report.

Tab. 4-1: Range and detection limits of the infra-red detectors, portable Ecoprobe-5™ instrument (RS Dynamics)

Gas	Range (%vol)	Range (ppm)	Detection limit (ppm)
CO ₂	0 - 50	0 - 500 000	20
CH ₄	0 - 50	0 - 500 000	100
TP	0 - 50	0 - 500 000	30
O ₂	0- 100	0 - 1 000 000	100

Periodical soil gas monitoring results are presented as 2D contour maps created in Surfer 13™ of Golden Software using kriging interpolation method.

4.2 Continuous monitoring

The continuous monitoring of CO₂ in soil gas was performed using permanent probes (Fig. 4-2) manufactured by Sapienza University of Rome and Idogeosol company. The measuring range of CO₂ is 0-500 000 ppm with a detection limit of 100 ppm. Hourly sampling interval was selected resulting in 24 measured values a day. The probes were buried 60-80 cm below the ground surface at 5 monitoring points (29, 102, 106, 120 and 123). The CO₂ content in soil gas was measured since June 2021 to October 2023. The main aim of continuous monitoring was to detect the seasonal and daily variation trends and to evaluate the influence of weather conditions.

Fig. 4-2: Permanent probes used for continuous soil gas monitoring above the Zar-3 oil & gas field.

4.3 Supplementary data

Meteorological data, such as temperature (°C), relative humidity (%) and atmospheric pressure (hPa) were measured 1.5 m above the ground level by the Comet instrument calibrated by the publicly available meteorological data of the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute at the Brno – Tuřany airport located 23.5 km to the NW. Precipitation (mm) and wind and gust speed (m/s) including the direction (°) were used from the same source (CHMU, 2023) and supplemented by the data from World Weather Online web page (www.worldweatheronline.com/brno-weather-history/jihomoravsky-kraj/cz.aspx) and Weather Underground web page (<https://www.wunderground.com/weather/cz/brno/LKTB>).

5 RESULTS

5.1 Periodical monitoring

Strong variability of CO₂ content in soil gas is observed. Seasonal vegetation and microbiological activities are interpreted as the main controlling factor of CO₂ in soil gas. The highest CO₂ content was measured in summer-autumn campaigns (9.67 %_{vol} in 2021, 6.42%_{vol} in 2022 and 6.28%_{vol} in 2023) with trends of spring increase and autumn decrease. The minimum CO₂ content in soil gas – typically below 0.5%_{vol} – was measured in winter campaigns. Fig. 5-1 summarizes all monitoring campaigns showing similarities in CO₂ in soil gas patterns among seasons in different years. Maps in Fig. 5-1 are ordered by years in rows and seasons in columns.

Fig. 5-1: Average CO₂ content in soil gas in all 8 monitoring campaigns with comparable CO₂ in soil gas patterns highlighted.

The rainfall total was identified as the second most important factor controlling the CO₂ content in soil gas. The 2021 and 2023 were typical by high rainfalls and higher CO₂ in soil gas, as compared to dry 2022 with lower CO₂ content in soil gas. For the ranges of CO₂ in soil gas, see Tab. 5-1.

Average CO₂ in soil gas for 3 springs, 3 summer-autumns and 2 winter monitoring campaigns calculated from the seasonal data sets are in Fig. 5-2 (winter 2021/2022 and 2022/2023), Fig. 5-3 (spring 2021, 2022 and 2023) and Fig. 5-4 (summer-autumn 2021, 2022 and 2023). These maps suppress the effect of weather variations and represent the areal baseline pattern of the CO₂ in soil gas in Zar-3.

Tab. 5-1: CO₂ (%_{vol}) in soil gas: range is given as numerator, averages as denominator; number of monitoring points in parentheses below the land use

Campaign	Land use	Field (67)	Grass (20)	Grove (8)	All (95)
1. spring 2021		<u>0.07 – 6.14</u> 1.05	<u>0.08 – 9.09</u> 2.81	<u>0.50 – 3.69</u> 2.05	<u>0.07 – 9.09</u> 1.51
2. summer-autumn 2021		<u>0.06 – 9.67</u> 2.25	<u>0.26 – 6.93</u> 3.32	<u>0.46 – 5.00</u> 2.29	<u>0.06 – 9.67</u> 2.47
3. winter 2021-2022		<u>0.07 – 2.33</u> 0.35	<u>0.09 – 0.85</u> 0.46	<u>0.07 – 1.29</u> 0.51	<u>0.07 – 2.33</u> 0.38
4. spring 2022		<u>0.09 – 3.09</u> 0.52	<u>0.12 – 5.23</u> 1.10	<u>0.18 – 2.26</u> 0.98	<u>0.09 – 5.23</u> 0.68
5. summer-autumn 2022		<u>0.12 – 2.21</u> 0.60	<u>0.18 – 6.42</u> 2.23	<u>0.32 – 2.44</u> 0.87	<u>0.12 – 6.42</u> 0.97
6. winter 2022-2023		<u>0.04 – 1.52</u> 0.18	<u>0.07 – 1.25</u> 0.41	<u>0.10 – 1.06</u> 0.38	<u>0.04 – 1.52</u> 0.25
7. spring 2023		<u>0.09 – 4.38</u> 1.07	<u>0.96 – 5.61</u> 2.27	<u>1.32 – 2.88</u> 2.25	<u>0.09 – 5.61</u> 1.42
8. summer-autumn 2023		<u>0.30 – 5.40</u> 1.28	<u>0.76 – 5.72</u> 2.31	<u>0.38 – 6.28</u> 1.82	<u>0.30 – 6.28</u> 1.54

Fig. 5-2: Average CO₂ content in soil gas in winter 2021/2022 and 2022/2023.

Fig. 5-3: Average CO₂ content in soil gas in spring of 2021, 2022 and 2023.

Fig. 5-4: Average CO₂ content in soil gas in summer-autumn of 2021, 2022 and 2023.

The land use represents the third most important factor. Average content of CO₂ in soil gas according to the land use is shown in Fig. 5-5. The grasslands and forests show much stronger difference in soil gas composition between summer and winter when compared to cultivated fields. Cultivation and mainly ploughing takes place in early spring and later autumn results in stronger devolatilization of soils. Arable fields show in general lower sampling under-pressure indicating higher permeability of the soil profile. Our interpretation is that this is the reason why fields have markedly lower CO₂ content in soil gas when compared with grasslands and forests.

Fig. 5-5: Average CO₂ content in soil gas according to the land use and individual monitoring campaigns.

No methane, nor the total petroleum anomalies were detected in soil gas above the Zar-3 oil & gas field during the baseline monitoring (Fig. 5-6). The maximum CH₄ values in soil gas were < 0.5 %_{vol} and were not confirmed by repeated measurements at the same place, nor in different seasons. For the ranges of CH₄ in soil gas, see Tab. 5-2. The methane content in soil gas of < 0.5 %_{vol} is usual, not anomalous in wet soils. It is caused by microbiological methanogenic activity and, in case of cultivated agricultural fields, may be enhanced by manure field fertilization (e.g. Summer-Autumn monitoring campaign held in Sep 22; labelled in Fig. 5-6).

It is worth noting, that the methane lower explosive limit (LEL) and lower flammability limit (LFL) at atmospheric temperature and pressure conditions is 5.3% for LEL and 4.4% for LFL.

To evaluate the potential leakage pathways via existing wells, the soil gas measurements of both well hubs (production platforms) of the Zar-3 oil & gas field was carried out in February 2023. The maximum measured CH₄ content was 0.6 %_{vol}. The soil gas composition was measured during the winter season, when, in general, negligible interference by biological methanogenic activity was observed. The boreholes in operation above the Zar-3 oil & gas field are regarded as tight with no leakage indications based on the soil gas monitoring campaign. For further information, see the V4 – Risk assessment report (Ford et al. 2023) of the Work Package 6: Risk analysis.

Fig. 5-6: Average CH₄ content in soil gas in all 8 monitoring campaigns. The highest measured CH₄ content of < 0.5 % is usual, not anomalous in soils.

Tab. 5-2: CH₄ (ppm) in soil gas: range is given as numerator, averages in denominator; number of monitoring points in parentheses below the land use

Campaign	Land use	Field (67)	Grass (20)	Grove (8)	All (95)
1. spring 2021		$\frac{0-9}{0}$	$\frac{0-14}{1}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-14}{0}$
2. summer-autumn 2021		$\frac{0-1649}{48}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-540}{68}$	$\frac{0-1649}{40}$
3. winter 2021-2022		$\frac{0-4824}{203}$	$\frac{0-1381}{134}$	$\frac{0-3023}{595}$	$\frac{0-4824}{221}$
4. spring 2022		$\frac{0-484}{28}$	$\frac{0-114}{10}$	$\frac{0-275}{53}$	$\frac{0-484}{27}$
5. summer-autumn 2022		$\frac{0-4621}{603}$	$\frac{0-4048}{234}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-4621}{474}$
6. winter 2022-2023		$\frac{0-1256}{64}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-1256}{45}$
7. spring 2023		$\frac{0-264}{5}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-0}{0}$	$\frac{0-264}{4}$
8. summer-autumn 2023		$\frac{0-1256}{132}$	$\frac{0-1196}{161}$	$\frac{0-405}{93}$	$\frac{0-1256}{135}$

5.2 Continuous monitoring

Content of CO₂ in soil gas measured by permanent probes (Fig. 5-7) provide much more detailed data set with trend of spring increase, summer maximum, autumn decrease and winter minimum observed in periodical monitoring. The measured annual maximum CO₂ content in soil gas was up to 9 %_{vol} in summer 2021 but only up to 6 %_{vol} in 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 5-7). The differences are interpreted as a result of vegetation and microbiological activity related to the weather conditions (Fig. 5-8). Strong increase in CO₂ in soil gas correspond to the period after strong rainfalls (labelled in Fig. 5-8). All the permanent probes have been placed in grasslands to exclude the potential effects of the land use and soil devolatilization. The differences among the trends measured by individual permanent probes (shown in colours in Fig. 5-8) are primarily caused by different soil types, water table level and vegetation in situ. The highest values (green line in Figs. 5-7 and 5-8) were observed in the valley floodplain with clayey low permeability on top of the soil profile. The lowest CO₂ values were observed on hilltops in more sandy soils.

Fig. 5-7: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes. For probe locations see Fig. 3-1. Timing of the periodical monitoring campaigns (usually 3-4 days) are marked by blue pointers.

Fig. 5-8: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes compared by the most important weather conditions factors – precipitation/ rainfall total, atmospheric pressure and atmospheric temperature.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The report summarizes the atmogeochemical monitoring in the Zar-3 pilot CO₂ storage complex situated in the Žarosice oil & gas field. It includes a brief introduction to the characteristics of the land use and pedology.

Detailed baseline soil gas monitoring above the Zar-3 oil & gas field was performed to determine potential soil gas anomalies, soil gas distribution and to improve the knowledge of the seal efficiency.

Strong variability of CO₂ content in soil gas is observed. The highest CO₂ content was measured in summer-autumn seasons with trends of spring increase and autumn decrease. The minimum CO₂ content in soil gas was measured in winter seasons. Similarities in patterns of CO₂ in soil gas in the specific seasons are observed in 2-3 years.

Seasonal vegetation and microbiological activities are interpreted as the main controlling factor of CO₂ in soil gas. The second most important factor is rainfall total, followed by land use. The atmospheric pressure shows an hourly-rated impact and is in general less important.

Neither methane, nor the total petroleum anomalies were detected in soil gas above the Zar-3 oil & gas field during the baseline monitoring. The maximum CH₄ values in soil gas were < 0.5 %_{vol} and were not confirmed by repeated measurements at the same place, nor in different seasons.

The CO₂ baseline carried out over multiple seasons makes it possible to quantify the natural variability and to establish the threshold values that could indicate the potential leakage. The results will serve as a background for the future monitoring measurements during and after the true CO₂ storage making it possible to identify newly formed anomalies, if any. The experience learned during the baseline soil gas monitoring will serve as a basis for the main result of Site monitoring plan prepared in Task 7.5.

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ATTACHMENTS – MONITORING DATASETS

Attachment 1: 1st periodical monitoring campaign: spring 2021

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	fresh planting	-100.5	18.3	21.8	0.00	0.00	0.08	6.5.21 8:40
2	Field	no vegetation	-6.5	19.4	21.5	0.00	0.00	0.83	6.5.21 8:45
3	Field	fresh planting	-5.3	19.6	21.0	0.00	0.00	0.48	6.5.21 9:06
4	Field	fresh planting	-85.3	18.3	21.3	0.00	0.00	0.11	6.5.21 9:01
5	Field	fresh planting	-56.7	18.9	21.5	0.00	0.00	0.13	6.5.21 8:55
6	Field	fresh planting	-98.8	17.5	21.5	0.00	0.00	0.60	6.5.21 8:52
7	Field	fresh planting	-140.4	17.4	20.9	0.00	0.00	0.08	6.5.21 9:16
8	Field	fresh planting	-2.5	19.7	20.9	0.00	0.00	0.41	6.5.21 9:21
9	Field	fresh planting	-28.9	19.3	21.1	0.00	0.00	0.13	6.5.21 9:25
10	Field	fresh planting	-48.4	18.8	21.4	0.00	0.00	0.23	6.5.21 9:32
11	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-10.0	19.3	21.4	0.00	0.00	0.59	6.5.21 9:36
12	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-6.1	18.6	21.5	0.00	0.00	1.75	6.5.21 9:40
13	Field	fresh planting	-285.7	14.5	21.2	0.00	0.00	0.07	6.5.21 10:16
14	Grass	grass	-10.0	19.7	21.1	0.00	0.00	0.23	6.5.21 10:07
15	Field	fresh planting	-30.9	18.8	21.4	0.00	0.00	0.65	6.5.21 10:01
16	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-17.9	19.3	21.5	0.00	0.00	0.48	6.5.21 9:56
17	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-9.4	19.0	21.5	0.00	0.00	1.29	6.5.21 9:51
18	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-12.6	18.7	21.5	0.00	0.00	1.36	6.5.21 9:46
19	Grass	grass	-3.1	19.3	20.2	0.00	0.00	1.06	6.5.21 16:16
20	Field	fresh planting	-1.1	19.8	20.3	0.00	0.00	0.64	6.5.21 16:08
21	Grass	grass	-20.1	18.9	20.5	0.00	0.00	1.11	6.5.21 10:25
22	Field	fresh planting	-6.9	18.5	20.2	0.00	0.00	1.42	6.5.21 10:46
23	Field	fresh planting	-222.8	15.8	20.5	0.00	0.00	0.09	6.5.21 10:50
24	Field	fresh planting	-23.4	18.9	20.6	0.00	0.00	0.96	6.5.21 10:57
25	Field	fresh planting	-9.1	19.5	20.8	0.00	0.00	0.65	6.5.21 11:01
26	Field	fresh planting	-4.0	19.3	21.1	0.00	0.00	0.97	6.5.21 11:42
27	Field	fresh planting	-40.4	17.5	21.3	0.00	0.00	1.49	6.5.21 11:37
28	Grove	grove	-2.7	19.0	21.3	0.00	0.00	1.30	6.5.21 11:30
29	Field	fresh planting	-18.5	16.4	21.5	0.00	0.00	3.21	6.5.21 11:19
30	Field	fresh planting	-67.5	18.1	21.6	0.00	0.00	0.72	6.5.21 11:15
31	Field	fresh planting	-6.7	19.2	21.4	0.00	0.00	0.75	6.5.21 11:11
32	Field	fresh planting	-16.0	19.5	21.1	0.00	0.00	0.29	6.5.21 11:06
33	Field	fresh planting	-91.5	16.6	21.1	0.00	0.00	1.16	6.5.21 11:50
34	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-135.0	16.2	21.2	0.00	0.00	0.91	6.5.21 11:54
35	Field	fresh planting	-4.1	19.5	21.1	0.00	0.00	0.59	6.5.21 12:00
36	Field	fresh planting	-24.1	18.1	21.2	0.00	0.00	1.20	6.5.21 12:06
37	Field	fresh planting	-143.7	17.1	21.5	0.00	0.00	0.09	6.5.21 12:15
38	Grove	grove	-108.7	17.3	21.5	0.00	0.00	0.50	6.5.21 12:20
39	Grove	grove	-3.6	18.2	21.3	0.00	0.00	2.10	6.5.21 12:25
40	Field	fresh planting	-160.6	16.9	23.1	0.00	0.00	0.21	6.5.21 13:22
41	Field	fresh planting	-24.4	18.4	22.7	0.00	0.00	0.68	6.5.21 13:18
42	Field	fresh planting	-107.0	17.2	22.5	0.00	0.00	0.81	6.5.21 13:11
43	Field	fresh planting	-160.0	14.9	22.4	0.00	0.00	1.49	6.5.21 13:07
44	Grove	grove	-4.2	19.4	21.7	0.00	0.00	0.66	6.5.21 13:02
45	Grass	grassland	-1.3	19.9	21.4	0.00	0.00	0.08	6.5.21 12:58
46	Field	fresh planting	-170.2	16.6	21.1	0.00	0.00	0.08	6.5.21 12:47
47	Field	fresh planting	-168.1	16.4	23.3	0.00	0.00	0.18	6.5.21 13:30
48	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-6.4	19.0	23.2	0.00	0.00	1.07	6.5.21 13:35
49	Field	fresh planting	-219.7	14.4	23.7	0.00	0.00	0.74	6.5.21 13:43
50	Field	fresh planting	-191.6	13.5	23.8	0.00	0.00	1.29	6.5.21 13:48
51	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-149.9	16.5	23.6	0.00	0.00	0.60	6.5.21 14:02
52	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-145.6	16.9	24.2	0.00	0.00	0.14	6.5.21 14:09
53	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-15.2	17.4	24.4	0.00	0.00	3.02	6.5.21 14:14

54	Field	fresh planting	-202.8	15.8	23.9	0.00	0.00	0.08	6.5.21 14:45
55	Field	fresh planting	-3.5	19.1	23.9	0.00	0.00	0.61	6.5.21 14:39
56	Grass	grassland	-15.6	19.1	24.1	0.00	0.00	0.73	6.5.21 14:34
57	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-18.0	18.3	24.3	0.00	0.00	2.20	6.5.21 14:29
58	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-5.2	17.6	24.5	0.00	0.00	3.24	6.5.21 14:24
59	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-27.3	18.1	24.6	0.00	0.00	2.06	6.5.21 14:20
60	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-178.7	15.6	23.8	0.00	0.00	1.04	6.5.21 14:51
61	Field	fresh planting	-1.4	19.6	23.3	0.00	0.00	0.35	6.5.21 14:55
62	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-3.9	19.1	23.2	0.00	0.00	1.27	6.5.21 15:00
63	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-29.2	17.2	23.3	0.00	0.00	3.22	6.5.21 15:04
64	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-1.6	19.3	23.1	0.00	0.00	0.70	6.5.21 15:08
65	Field	oilfield rape (40 cm)	-155.8	16.7	23.1	0.00	0.00	0.24	6.5.21 15:29
66	Field	oilfield rape (40 cm)	-1.7	19.4	22.9	0.00	0.00	0.49	6.5.21 15:23
67	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-2.4	19.3	22.9	0.00	0.00	0.67	6.5.21 15:19
68	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-1.8	19.3	23.1	0.00	0.00	0.80	6.5.21 15:14
101	Grass	grass (dry)	-1.5	18.0	21.0	0.00	0.00	3.60	3.6.21 8:30
102	Grass	grass (mown)	-126.3	9.7	22.6	0.00	0.00	5.08	3.6.21 8:40
103	Field	sunflower	-197.2	13.7	25.1	0.00	0.00	0.63	3.6.21 8:54
104	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-5.1	17.7	26.8	0.00	0.00	3.03	3.6.21 9:10
105	Grass	grass (80 cm)	-6.6	15.9	27.7	0.00	0.00	6.63	3.6.21 9:23
106	Field	corn	-119.6	13.4	28.4	0.00	0.00	6.14	3.6.21 9:33
107	Field	barley field	-10.4	17.6	29.1	0.00	0.00	2.60	3.6.21 9:46
108	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.9	16.0	29.4	0.00	0.00	4.49	3.6.21 9:55
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.7	16.9	30.0	0.00	0.00	4.35	3.6.21 10:02
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-104.6	15.0	30.6	0.00	0.00	3.40	3.6.21 10:13
111	Grass	grass (mown)	-10.0	16.9	30.6	0.00	0.00	2.72	3.6.21 10:23
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-3.5	19.0	31.2	0.00	0.00	1.19	3.6.21 10:34
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-62.0	16.0	31.2	0.00	0.00	3.51	3.6.21 10:43
114	Grove	orchard	-13.5	18.6	31.4	0.00	0.00	1.68	3.6.21 10:59
115	Grass	grass	-166.5	14.3	31.2	0.00	0.00	2.27	3.6.21 11:13
116	Grass	grass (80 cm)	-5.8	17.4	31.6	0.00	0.00	2.93	3.6.21 11:24
117	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-4.0	19.2	32.0	0.00	0.00	0.85	3.6.21 11:29
118	Field	wheat (50 cm)	-11.0	18.8	32.5	0.00	0.00	1.12	3.6.21 11:49
119	Grove	grove	-4.8	17.0	32.9	0.00	0.00	3.62	3.6.21 12:14
120	Field	wheat (50 cm)	-11.9	17.9	33.2	0.00	0.00	2.04	3.6.21 12:28
121	Grass	grass (mown)	-50.2	17.8	33.7	0.00	0.00	1.52	3.6.21 13:47
122	Grove	grove	-2.9	17.4	34.4	0.00	0.00	3.69	3.6.21 14:00
123	Grass	grass (mown)	-124.1	11.1	34.8	0.00	0.00	9.09	3.6.21 14:10
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-79.3	17.1	34.2	0.00	0.00	1.08	3.6.21 14:20
125	Grove	grove	-51.9	16.4	33.9	0.00	0.00	2.81	3.6.21 14:38
126	Grass	grass (mown)	-14.1	18.5	33.8	0.00	0.00	1.09	3.6.21 14:52
127	Field	pea plant	-158.9	13.7	34.5	0.00	0.00	2.43	3.6.21 15:05

Attachment 2: 2nd periodical monitoring campaign: summer-autumn 2021

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	corn (2 m)	-18.0	16.3	24.5	0.00	0.00	2.01	9.9.21 9:56
2	Field	no vegetation	-105.9	14.7	24.5	0.00	0.00	0.95	9.9.21 10:06
3	Field	corn (2 m)	-15.9	16.8	28.0	0.00	0.00	0.96	9.9.21 11:48
4	Field	corn (2 m)	-19.1	15.2	28.0	0.00	0.00	3.57	9.9.21 11:38
5	Field	corn (2 m)	-4.5	16.2	27.4	0.00	0.00	2.09	9.9.21 11:17
6	Field	corn (2 m)	-93.8	15.7	25.2	0.00	0.00	0.66	9.9.21 10:21
7	Field	corn (2 m)	-296.1	11.6	28.6	0.01	0.00	0.06	9.9.21 12:05
8	Field	corn (2 m)	-3.4	17.2	28.3	0.00	0.00	0.66	9.9.21 11:56
9	Field	corn (2 m)	-10.1	15.6	31.7	0.00	0.00	3.05	9.9.21 16:01
10	Field	corn (2 m)	-38.2	16.5	27.1	0.00	0.00	0.74	9.9.21 11:07
11	Field	ploughed field	-15.7	15.8	26.0	0.00	0.00	2.25	9.9.21 10:39
12	Field	ploughed field	-22.6	17.1	25.4	0.00	0.00	0.19	9.9.21 10:30
13	Field	corn (2 m)	-69.1	16.4	28.5	0.00	0.00	0.14	9.9.21 12:12
14	Grass	grass	-153.7	12.0	29.6	0.00	0.00	0.26	9.9.21 12:24
15	Field	corn (2 m)	-190.6	13.9	30.2	0.00	0.00	0.54	9.9.21 12:36
16	Field	ploughed field	-36.5	16.7	26.7	0.00	0.00	0.56	9.9.21 10:58
17	Field	ploughed field	-31.6	14.0	26.5	0.00	0.00	3.51	9.9.21 10:43
18	Field	ploughed field	-81.5	14.1	26.6	0.00	0.00	2.74	9.9.21 10:50
19	Grass	grass	-4.7	16.0	27.9	0.00	0.00	2.26	10.9.21 11:12
20	Field	ploughed field	-157.3	8.1	28.2	0.00	0.00	5.93	10.9.21 11:19
21	Grass	grass	-14.2	15.5	30.3	0.00	0.00	3.74	9.9.21 12:45
22	Field	corn (2 m)	-24.6	15.4	30.1	0.00	0.00	3.35	9.9.21 13:07
23	Field	corn (2 m)	-146.7	14.1	30.3	0.16	0.06	0.90	9.9.21 13:14
24	Field	corn (2 m)	-8.1	16.4	30.8	0.00	0.00	1.84	9.9.21 13:27
25	Field	corn (2 m)	-10.6	14.6	30.9	0.00	0.00	3.96	9.9.21 13:36
26	Field	corn (2 m)	-32.5	16.4	29.0	0.00	0.00	1.05	10.9.21 12:11
27	Field	corn (2 m)	-65.5	16.0	28.3	0.00	0.00	0.87	10.9.21 12:05
28	Grove	grove	-5.3	16.5	28.3	0.00	0.00	1.82	10.9.21 11:30
29	Field	corn (2 m)	-39.3	13.5	32.2	0.00	0.00	4.54	9.9.21 15:45
30	Field	corn (2 m)	-19.8	16.5	29.5	0.00	0.00	1.24	10.9.21 13:21
31	Field	corn (2 m)	-48.3	15.6	31.0	0.00	0.00	1.84	10.9.21 13:45
32	Field	corn (2 m)	-3.6	16.7	31.4	0.00	0.00	1.51	9.9.21 13:43
33	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-5.7	16.7	28.0	0.00	0.00	1.24	10.9.21 11:56
34	Field	ploughed field	-24.7	14.7	28.0	0.00	0.00	4.49	10.9.21 11:51
35	Field	corn (2 m)	-2.9	15.9	28.2	0.00	0.00	2.28	10.9.21 11:42
36	Field	corn (2 m)	-14.6	16.4	32.4	0.00	0.00	1.67	9.9.21 15:38
37	Field	corn (2 m)	-67.1	14.8	29.9	0.00	0.00	2.76	10.9.21 13:27
38	Grove	grove	-13.8	16.8	30.6	0.00	0.00	1.11	10.9.21 13:37
39	Grove	grove	-14.5	16.2	31.8	0.00	0.00	1.99	9.9.21 13:51
40	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-49.2	12.3	32.0	0.00	0.00	4.84	9.9.21 14:58
41	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-4.5	16.9	32.0	0.13	0.12	0.93	9.9.21 14:42
42	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-142.0	14.9	32.0	0.00	0.00	0.37	9.9.21 14:27
43	Field	corn (2 m)	-141.1	13.9	32.1	0.00	0.00	1.48	9.9.21 14:20
44	Grove	grove	-3.4	17.4	32.2	0.05	0.02	0.46	9.9.21 14:11
45	Grass	grass	-5.3	15.6	32.2	0.00	0.00	3.51	9.9.21 14:05
46	Field	ploughed field	-273.8	1.4	32.5	0.00	0.00	4.01	9.9.21 13:58
47	Field	ploughed field	-85.3	15.9	32.2	0.00	0.00	0.34	9.9.21 15:06
48	Field	ploughed field	-8.6	16.2	32.0	0.00	0.00	2.28	9.9.21 15:13
49	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-15.9	15.5	32.0	0.00	0.00	2.80	9.9.21 15:19
50	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-29.5	11.5	32.3	0.00	0.00	9.67	9.9.21 15:28
51	Field	ploughed field	-87.5	15.7	25.6	0.00	0.00	0.53	10.9.21 9:00
52	Field	ploughed field	-26.1	17.1	25.7	0.00	0.00	0.08	10.9.21 9:05
53	Field	ploughed field	-22.5	15.5	26.1	0.00	0.00	2.47	10.9.21 9:14
54	Field	corn (2 m)	-158.1	12.9	26.5	0.00	0.00	1.87	10.9.21 9:52
55	Field	corn (2 m)	-3.1	15.8	26.0	0.00	0.00	2.75	10.9.21 9:43
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-12.7	17.0	26.2	0.00	0.00	0.65	10.9.21 9:37

57	Field	ploughed field	-44.8	15.6	26.4	0.00	0.00	3.68	10.9.21 9:32
58	Field	ploughed field	-4.5	15.7	26.1	0.00	0.00	3.24	10.9.21 9:26
59	Field	ploughed field	-88.6	14.5	26.3	0.00	0.00	1.64	10.9.21 9:21
60	Field	ploughed field	-2.2	17.0	25.9	0.00	0.00	0.64	10.9.21 10:04
61	Field	corn (2 m)	-157.2	11.9	26.2	0.00	0.00	3.02	10.9.21 10:15
62	Field	ploughed field	-91.4	14.5	26.7	0.01	0.00	1.86	10.9.21 10:21
63	Field	ploughed field	-116.0	13.7	27.1	0.00	0.00	1.59	10.9.21 10:26
64	Field	ploughed field	-6.7	15.9	27.3	0.00	0.00	2.10	10.9.21 10:32
65	Field	ploughed field	-49.9	13.5	28.1	0.00	0.00	3.47	10.9.21 10:55
66	Field	ploughed field	-41.0	15.7	27.8	0.00	0.00	1.66	10.9.21 10:50
67	Field	ploughed field	-112.0	4.8	27.9	0.00	0.00	9.35	10.9.21 10:45
68	Field	ploughed field	-7.3	16.4	27.4	0.00	0.00	2.09	10.9.21 10:37
101	Grass	grass (unmown)	-7.2	12.3	26.2	0.00	0.00	6.93	16.9.21 10:06
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-113.2	12.7	26.5	0.00	0.00	3.95	16.9.21 10:14
103	Field	sunflower	-298.2	10.8	27.1	0.00	0.00	0.68	16.9.21 10:26
104	Field	ploughed field	-75.4	12.3	30.4	0.00	0.00	4.48	16.9.21 12:28
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-11.7	13.2	30.2	0.00	0.00	6.73	16.9.21 12:18
106	Field	corn field	-60.7	12.0	30.2	0.00	0.00	4.15	16.9.21 12:08
107	Field	barley? field	-18.6	15.5	27.7	0.00	0.00	1.95	16.9.21 10:41
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-5.3	14.0	28.2	0.00	0.00	5.64	16.9.21 10:49
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-3.3	15.4	28.7	0.00	0.00	3.06	16.9.21 10:58
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-4.5	14.9	29.7	0.00	0.01	4.18	16.9.21 11:20
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-4.5	15.3	29.3	0.00	0.03	3.49	16.9.21 11:09
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-6.3	16.2	30.4	0.00	0.00	1.53	16.9.21 11:43
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-12.1	14.9	30.3	0.00	0.00	3.61	16.9.21 11:50
114	Grove	orchard	-3.5	16.1	30.2	0.00	0.00	1.82	16.9.21 11:58
115	Grass	grass	-12.8	15.2	31.5	0.00	0.00	3.30	16.9.21 13:30
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-5.0	15.5	31.8	0.00	0.00	2.41	16.9.21 13:35
117	Field	ploughed field	-105.7	15.2	32.1	0.00	0.00	0.21	16.9.21 13:40
118	Field	ploughed field	-41.7	16.2	32.1	0.00	0.00	0.30	16.9.21 13:52
119	Grove	grove	-3.3	14.7	31.4	0.00	0.00	5.00	16.9.21 14:14
120	Field	ploughed field	-2.3	16.5	31.1	0.00	0.00	1.11	16.9.21 14:21
121	Grass	grass	-4.9	16.1	31.6	0.00	0.00	1.63	16.9.21 15:46
122	Grove	grove	-3.5	15.1	31.0	0.00	0.00	3.91	16.9.21 14:39
123	Grass	grass (mown)	-15.2	14.5	31.2	0.00	0.00	4.70	16.9.21 14:56
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-19.2	15.2	31.1	0.00	0.00	2.24	16.9.21 14:51
125	Grove	grove	-26.5	15.2	31.2	0.00	0.00	2.19	16.9.21 15:20
126	Grass	grass (mown)	-3.3	15.7	31.3	0.00	0.00	2.49	16.9.21 15:29
127	Field	ploughed field	-28.5	12.3	31.4	0.00	0.00	4.68	16.9.21 15:38

Attachment 3: 3rd periodical monitoring campaign: winter 2021-2022

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	ploughed corn field	-41.2	14.6	18.7	0.00	0.00	0.13	14.2.22 9:47
2	Field	no vegetation	-111.0	14.3	17.9	0.00	0.00	0.14	14.2.22 9:53
3	Field	ploughed corn field	-16.8	14.3	16.0	0.00	0.00	0.24	14.2.22 10:14
4	Field	ploughed corn field	-0.9	14.5	16.6	0.00	0.00	0.23	14.2.22 10:08
5	Field	ploughed corn field	-5.3	14.2	16.9	0.00	0.00	0.83	14.2.22 10:03
6	Field	ploughed corn field	-38.2	14.2	17.4	0.00	0.00	0.21	14.2.22 9:58
7	Field	ploughed field (very wet)	-177.9	11.6	15.9	0.00	0.00	0.49	14.2.22 10:19
8	Field	ploughed corn field	-2.3	14.5	15.5	0.00	0.00	0.13	14.2.22 10:26
9	Field	ploughed corn field	-5.2	14.3	15.5	0.00	0.00	0.49	14.2.22 10:31
10	Field	ploughed corn field	-19.0	14.2	15.5	0.00	0.00	0.12	14.2.22 10:37
11	Field	grain (10 cm)	-16.2	14.1	15.6	0.00	0.00	0.42	14.2.22 10:41
12	Field	grain (10 cm)	-4.0	14.2	15.5	0.00	0.00	0.62	14.2.22 10:47
13	Field	grain (10 cm), very wet	-135.5	13.9	15.4	0.00	0.00	0.07	14.2.22 11:20
14	Grass	grass	-3.2	14.1	15.2	0.00	0.02	0.66	14.2.22 11:12
15	Field	ploughed corn field	-4.3	14.5	15.4	0.00	0.00	0.13	14.2.22 11:06
16	Field	winter cereal	-15.9	14.3	15.5	0.00	0.00	0.13	14.2.22 11:00
17	Field	winter cereal	-37.2	14.3	15.6	0.00	0.00	0.33	14.2.22 10:56
18	Field	winter cereal	-6.3	14.2	15.6	0.00	0.00	0.74	14.2.22 10:51
19	Grass	grass	-88.2	13.5	14.9	0.12	0.36	0.50	14.2.22 12:55
20	Field	ploughed field (very wet)	-167.5	12.8	16.1	0.00	0.32	0.12	14.2.22 14:14
21	Grass	grass	-14.5	13.7	16.2	0.00	0.00	0.15	14.2.22 11:24
22	Field	ploughed corn field	-13.6	14.4	15.6	0.00	0.00	0.10	14.2.22 11:33
23	Field	ploughed corn field	-174.3	13.5	15.9	0.00	0.00	0.28	14.2.22 11:40
24	Field	ploughed corn field	-6.1	14.3	16.0	0.00	0.00	0.53	14.2.22 11:46
25	Field	ploughed corn field	-43.5	13.7	16.1	0.00	0.00	0.64	14.2.22 11:51
26	Field	ploughed corn field	-28.2	14.2	15.1	0.00	0.00	0.30	14.2.22 12:50
27	Field	ploughed corn field	-1.1	14.4	15.2	0.00	0.00	0.20	14.2.22 12:46
28	Grove	grove	-1.8	14.3	15.4	0.00	0.00	0.46	14.2.22 12:36
29	Field	ploughed corn field	-37.4	13.7	15.2	0.00	0.00	1.09	14.2.22 12:29
30	Field	ploughed corn field	-2.6	13.9	14.8	0.00	0.00	1.12	14.2.22 12:20
31	Field	ploughed corn field	-85.3	13.5	15.3	0.00	0.00	0.16	14.2.22 12:09
32	Field	ploughed corn field	-53.9	13.8	16.2	0.00	0.00	0.33	14.2.22 11:56
33	Field	winter cereal	-10.6	14.3	16.3	0.00	0.00	0.57	14.2.22 14:26
34	Field	ploughed field	-8.4	14.5	16.3	0.05	0.28	0.34	14.2.22 14:31
35	Field	ploughed corn field	-46.9	13.9	16.2	0.00	0.00	0.21	14.2.22 14:40
36	Field	ploughed corn field	-173.8	14.2	16.0	0.00	0.29	0.11	14.2.22 14:45
37	Field	ploughed corn field	-74.2	13.4	15.8	0.06	0.13	0.45	14.2.22 14:51
38	Grove	grove	-42.1	14.0	15.6	0.30	0.43	0.07	14.2.22 14:57
39	Grove	grove	-6.3	14.2	15.7	0.15	0.42	0.55	14.2.22 15:10
40	Field	winter cereal	-3.6	14.2	19.7	0.03	0.34	0.38	15.2.22 9:28
41	Field	winter cereal	-98.4	13.2	20.0	0.48	0.44	0.17	15.2.22 9:24
42	Field	winter cereal	-8.4	14.3	20.1	0.00	0.25	0.24	15.2.22 9:19
43	Field	ploughed corn field	-47.5	13.9	20.2	0.08	0.28	0.07	15.2.22 9:15
44	Grove	grove	-2.0	14.4	20.3	0.00	0.20	0.23	15.2.22 9:10
45	Grass	grass	-47.6	13.6	15.9	0.14	0.80	0.82	14.2.22 15:20
46	Field	ploughed field	-102.3	13.3	15.8	0.07	0.35	0.07	14.2.22 15:15
47	Field	ploughed corn field	-36.3	14.0	19.3	0.24	0.51	0.08	15.2.22 9:33
48	Field	ploughed field	-1.5	14.3	19.0	0.01	0.29	0.16	15.2.22 9:38
49	Field	winter cereal	-21.1	14.1	18.6	0.00	0.00	0.11	15.2.22 9:44
50	Field	winter cereal	-2.9	13.9	18.2	0.00	0.00	0.81	15.2.22 9:49
51	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-9.3	14.3	15.6	0.00	0.00	0.12	15.2.22 10:09

52	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-106.6	13.1	15.7	0.00	0.00	0.11	15.2.22 10:14
53	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-3.6	14.1	15.9	0.00	0.00	0.65	15.2.22 10:18
54	Field	ploughed (corn) field	-19.3	14.0	16.8	0.00	0.00	0.14	15.2.22 10:46
55	Field	ploughed (corn) field	-45.4	13.7	16.7	0.00	0.00	0.28	15.2.22 10:40
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-44.7	13.6	16.6	0.00	0.00	0.40	15.2.22 10:36
57	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-56.4	13.6	16.5	0.00	0.00	0.19	15.2.22 10:32
58	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-27.9	13.7	16.3	0.00	0.00	0.51	15.2.22 10:27
59	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-17.8	14.0	16.0	0.00	0.00	0.31	15.2.22 10:22
60	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-75.6	13.4	17.0	0.00	0.03	0.27	15.2.22 10:51
61	Field	ploughed (corn) field	-7.1	14.0	16.8	0.00	0.00	0.73	15.2.22 10:57
62	Field	winter cereal	-18.3	14.0	16.8	0.00	0.01	0.53	15.2.22 11:00
63	Field	winter cereal	-38.7	13.6	16.9	0.00	0.00	0.63	15.2.22 11:04
64	Field	winter cereal	-133.1	12.8	15.5	0.01	0.01	0.07	15.2.22 11:24
65	Field	winter cereal	-5.7	14.2	16.2	0.03	0.24	0.19	15.2.22 11:49
66	Field	winter cereal	-17.1	14.0	16.0	0.10	0.29	0.34	15.2.22 11:44
67	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-24.1	13.1	15.7	0.00	0.95	2.33	15.2.22 11:39
68	Field	ploughed (cereal?) field	-3.5	14.4	15.5	0.18	0.51	0.13	15.2.22 11:30
101	Grass	grass (unmown)	-13.5	14.2	20.0	0.00	0.00	0.37	16.2.22 10:11
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-10.6	14.3	20.3	0.00	0.00	0.11	16.2.22 10:21
103	Field	ploughed (sunflower) field	-1.8	14.4	19.3	0.00	0.00	0.12	16.2.22 10:40
104	Field	ploughed field	-2.7	14.3	18.9	0.00	0.00	0.18	16.2.22 10:51
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-6.7	14.3	18.4	0.00	0.00	0.09	16.2.22 11:15
106	Field	ploughed (corn) field	-2.5	14.4	18.3	0.00	0.00	0.10	16.2.22 11:03
107	Field	winter cereal	-12.1	14.2	18.7	0.00	0.00	0.09	16.2.22 11:25
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-2.0	13.8	19.4	0.00	0.00	0.63	16.2.22 11:41
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.3	13.9	17.4	0.00	0.00	0.67	15.2.22 12:36
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-4.6	13.9	18.8	0.00	0.00	0.85	16.2.22 12:42
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-78.1	13.3	16.8	0.00	0.00	0.49	15.2.22 12:29
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-27.5	14.0	16.5	0.00	0.00	0.34	15.2.22 12:22
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-24.3	13.9	16.4	0.01	0.37	0.73	15.2.22 12:14
114	Grove	orchard	-5.7	14.1	16.1	0.02	0.37	0.69	15.2.22 12:07
115	Grass	grass	-5.1	14.0	18.0	0.00	0.01	0.79	16.2.22 13:32
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-2.6	14.2	18.5	0.00	0.00	0.16	16.2.22 13:43
117	Field	winter cereal	-8.8	14.1	18.6	0.00	0.00	0.08	16.2.22 13:50
118	Field	weeds	-4.7	14.2	18.2	0.00	0.00	0.08	16.2.22 14:00
119	Grove	grove	-2.5	13.9	18.7	0.00	0.00	0.58	16.2.22 12:25
120	Field	weeds	-2.6	14.3	18.6	0.00	0.00	0.16	16.2.22 11:59
121	Grass	grass	-3.6	14.2	15.3	0.00	0.00	0.10	16.2.22 15:54
122	Grove	grove	-1.6	13.8	17.0	0.00	0.00	1.29	16.2.22 14:28
123	Grass	grass	-2.6	14.1	16.8	0.00	0.00	0.33	16.2.22 14:36
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-3.6	13.9	16.4	0.00	0.00	0.68	16.2.22 14:55
125	Grove	grove	-9.8	13.8	16.0	0.00	0.00	0.21	16.2.22 15:08
126	Grass	grass	-1.9	13.9	15.6	0.00	0.00	0.38	16.2.22 15:38
127	Field	winter cereal	-11.7	13.7	15.8	0.00	0.00	0.68	16.2.22 15:23

Attachment 4: 4th periodical monitoring campaign: spring 2022

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	wheat (30 cm)	-20.1	12.0	22.8	0.00	0.00	0.43	15.5.22 8:56
2	Field	no vegetation	-4.8	11.8	23.2	0.00	0.00	0.89	15.5.22 9:04
3	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-10.3	12.0	25.2	0.00	0.00	0.50	15.5.22 9:27
4	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.6	12.1	24.9	0.00	0.01	0.33	15.5.22 9:22
5	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-8.9	11.9	24.4	0.00	0.00	0.69	15.5.22 9:16
6	Field	wheat (30 cm)	-2.3	12.0	24.1	0.01	0.02	0.52	15.5.22 9:11
7	Field	wheat (very wet)	-4.0	12.2	25.5	0.00	0.00	0.24	15.5.22 9:33
8	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-8.9	12.2	25.7	0.00	0.00	0.29	15.5.22 9:37
9	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-14.2	11.9	25.8	0.00	0.00	0.67	15.5.22 9:42
10	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-90.1	11.2	26.4	0.00	0.00	0.29	15.5.22 9:47
11	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-19.0	12.2	26.9	0.00	0.00	0.41	15.5.22 9:54
12	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-4.5	12.1	27.5	0.00	0.00	0.67	15.5.22 9:58
13	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.8	12.2	30.0	0.05	0.04	0.43	15.5.22 10:26
14	Grass	grass	-10.7	12.4	29.7	0.00	0.01	0.14	15.5.22 10:21
15	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-16.1	12.2	29.3	0.00	0.00	0.42	15.5.22 10:16
16	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-7.8	12.3	28.9	0.00	0.00	0.25	15.5.22 10:12
17	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-22.8	12.0	28.6	0.00	0.02	0.51	15.5.22 10:07
18	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-19.3	11.9	28.2	0.00	0.00	0.74	15.5.22 10:03
19	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.7	12.4	36.4	0.00	0.00	0.90	16.5.22 12:59
20	Field	wheat (20 cm)	-72.3	11.7	37.0	0.00	0.00	0.59	16.5.22 13:09
21	Grass	grass	-181.7	11.0	30.3	0.00	0.00	0.37	15.5.22 10:35
22	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-39.7	12.1	30.7	0.00	0.02	0.27	15.5.22 10:40
23	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-56.0	11.9	30.6	0.03	0.02	0.12	15.5.22 10:46
24	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-75.8	11.7	31.0	0.00	0.00	0.24	15.5.22 10:52
25	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-2.6	12.1	31.8	0.00	0.00	0.82	15.5.22 13:36
26	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.3	12.5	33.0	0.00	0.00	0.56	15.5.22 14:15
27	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-17.7	12.3	33.4	0.00	0.00	0.63	15.5.22 14:11
28	Grove	grove	-6.7	12.5	33.9	0.00	0.00	0.36	15.5.22 14:03
29	Field	sunflower (20 cm)	-36.2	10.2	37.3	0.00	0.00	3.09	16.5.22 13:35
30	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-232.1	9.7	33.5	0.00	0.00	0.36	15.5.22 13:51
31	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-2.7	12.5	32.7	0.00	0.00	0.28	15.5.22 13:46
32	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-35.7	12.1	32.3	0.03	0.01	0.14	15.5.22 13:40
33	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.5	12.4	32.6	0.00	0.00	0.83	15.5.22 14:21
34	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-7.7	12.4	32.4	0.00	0.00	0.64	15.5.22 14:26
35	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.4	12.5	32.4	0.00	0.00	0.47	15.5.22 14:31
36	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-15.5	12.2	32.3	0.00	0.00	0.40	15.5.22 14:37
37	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-28.5	12.5	32.1	0.00	0.02	0.09	15.5.22 14:49
38	Grove	grove	-4.6	12.5	32.8	0.00	0.00	0.39	15.5.22 14:56
39	Grove	grove	-3.8	12.5	33.3	0.01	0.01	0.18	15.5.22 15:03
40	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-109.9	11.6	25.8	0.00	0.00	0.42	16.5.22 9:35
41	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-55.8	11.4	24.7	0.00	0.00	0.28	16.5.22 9:28
42	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-7.4	12.0	23.5	0.00	0.00	0.23	16.5.22 9:22
43	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-10.5	12.6	35.6	0.00	0.00	0.25	15.5.22 15:26
44	Grove	grove	-2.3	12.6	35.3	0.03	0.01	0.18	15.5.22 15:22
45	Grass	grass	-3.1	12.3	34.8	0.00	0.00	0.60	15.5.22 15:16
46	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-11.9	12.4	34.1	0.00	0.00	0.09	15.5.22 15:12
47	Field	corn (15 cm)	-3.2	11.9	26.7	0.00	0.00	0.43	16.5.22 9:42
48	Field	corn (15 cm)	-22.3	11.6	27.5	0.00	0.00	0.60	16.5.22 9:48
49	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-4.3	12.0	28.2	0.00	0.00	0.44	16.5.22 9:55
50	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-54.4	11.9	28.4	0.00	0.00	0.28	16.5.22 10:10
51	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-202.6	9.9	29.3	0.00	0.00	0.45	16.5.22 10:18
52	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-6.8	12.1	29.9	0.00	0.00	0.19	16.5.22 10:25
53	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-10.7	11.7	30.4	0.00	0.00	0.79	16.5.22 10:30
54	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-27.1	12.0	33.2	0.00	0.00	0.27	16.5.22 11:06
55	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-33.5	11.5	32.8	0.00	0.00	0.73	16.5.22 11:01
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-38.9	11.8	32.4	0.01	0.00	0.26	16.5.22 10:57

57	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-4.7	12.2	32.0	0.00	0.00	0.42	16.5.22 10:51
58	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.5	12.2	31.7	0.00	0.00	0.28	16.5.22 10:45
59	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.5	12.1	31.2	0.00	0.00	0.37	16.5.22 10:39
60	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-30.1	12.0	33.6	0.00	0.00	0.33	16.5.22 11:12
61	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-9.3	12.2	33.9	0.02	0.00	0.40	16.5.22 11:18
62	Field	corn (15 cm)	-9.5	12.3	34.2	0.00	0.00	0.20	16.5.22 11:23
63	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.3	12.4	34.7	0.00	0.00	0.57	16.5.22 11:34
64	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-2.1	12.4	34.7	0.00	0.00	0.60	16.5.22 11:37
65	Field	oat? (40 cm)	-2.0	12.4	35.1	0.00	0.00	0.57	16.5.22 11:58
66	Field	oat? (40 cm)	-2.2	12.6	35.0	0.00	0.00	0.19	16.5.22 11:53
67	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-35.3	12.1	34.8	0.00	0.00	0.63	16.5.22 11:47
68	Field	corn (15 cm)	-29.7	12.1	34.6	0.00	0.00	0.34	16.5.22 11:43
101	Grass	grass (unmown)	-40.5	11.3	19.5	0.00	0.00	1.59	14.5.22 11:20
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-17.7	11.9	31.7	0.00	0.00	1.30	18.5.22 13:26
103	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-5.1	12.1	24.4	0.00	0.00	0.47	14.5.22 12:12
104	Field	field	-2.3	12.5	33.0	0.00	0.00	0.41	18.5.22 13:09
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-13.6	11.8	33.3	0.00	0.00	1.71	18.5.22 12:56
106	Field	field	-2.1	11.8	27.5	0.00	0.00	1.33	14.5.22 12:45
107	Field	oilfield rape	-9.6	12.1	29.5	0.00	0.00	0.57	14.5.22 14:17
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-2.3	11.5	28.0	0.00	0.00	1.96	14.5.22 13:12
109	Grass	grass (unmown)	-14.9	11.9	31.7	0.00	0.00	1.17	18.5.22 13:34
110	Grass	grass (unmown)	-33.7	11.4	31.9	0.00	0.01	0.98	18.5.22 12:30
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-175.5	9.8	32.1	0.00	0.00	2.23	14.5.22 16:01
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.5	12.4	31.2	0.00	0.00	0.48	14.5.22 15:16
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-3.1	12.5	31.3	0.00	0.00	0.12	14.5.22 15:03
114	Grove	orchard	-7.6	12.0	30.3	0.00	0.00	1.06	14.5.22 14:35
115	Grass	grass	-65.9	11.8	38.0	0.01	0.00	0.26	16.5.22 14:01
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-157.7	10.6	38.3	0.00	0.00	0.44	16.5.22 14:14
117	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-20.6	12.3	37.9	0.02	0.01	0.41	16.5.22 14:21
118	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-13.8	12.6	37.6	0.03	0.02	0.11	16.5.22 14:33
119	Grove	grove	-4.6	11.6	23.5	0.00	0.00	1.19	18.5.22 9:40
120	Field	weeds	-6.0	11.7	23.9	0.00	0.00	1.44	18.5.22 8:58
121	Grass	grass (mown)	-8.6	11.9	27.4	0.00	0.00	0.79	18.5.22 11:20
122	Grove	grove	-2.2	11.8	38.2	0.00	0.00	2.26	16.5.22 14:45
123	Grass	grass	-110.1	8.2	23.6	0.00	0.00	5.23	18.5.22 10:03
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-24.8	11.6	24.4	0.00	0.00	0.72	18.5.22 10:14
125	Grove	grove	-7.5	11.2	25.7	0.00	0.00	2.20	18.5.22 10:32
126	Grass	grass	-27.6	11.6	26.3	0.00	0.00	0.70	18.5.22 10:47
127	Field	pea plant	-20.6	11.4	26.8	0.00	0.00	1.65	18.5.22 11:01

Attachment 5: 5th periodical monitoring campaign: summer-autumn 2022

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-3.2	8.6	25.1	0.00	0.03	0.39	13.9.22 10:13
2	Field	no vegetation	-58.1	8.0	25.6	0.00	0.04	0.76	13.9.22 10:18
3	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-26.5	8.5	27.9	0.00	0.06	0.25	13.9.22 10:49
4	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-25.3	8.5	27.5	0.00	0.06	0.26	13.9.22 10:43
5	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-20.3	8.4	26.8	0.00	0.06	0.45	13.9.22 10:32
6	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-87.0	7.9	26.4	0.00	0.05	0.38	13.9.22 10:28
7	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-54.7	8.5	28.3	0.00	0.07	0.16	13.9.22 10:54
8	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-15.9	8.6	28.7	0.00	0.08	0.33	13.9.22 11:03
9	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-31.9	8.6	29.2	0.00	0.09	0.21	13.9.22 11:09
10	Field	harvested wheat field, weed	-15.8	8.7	29.4	0.00	0.10	0.22	13.9.22 11:13
11	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-9.8	8.8	29.8	0.00	0.02	0.17	13.9.22 11:22
12	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-33.8	8.4	30.1	0.00	0.00	0.74	13.9.22 11:26
13	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-42.3	8.5	30.4	0.00	0.10	0.50	13.9.22 12:23
14	Grass	grass	-49.1	8.5	29.6	0.00	0.00	0.28	13.9.22 12:13
15	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-147.6	8.8	30.2	0.00	0.01	0.12	13.9.22 11:50
16	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-2.6	8.9	30.3	0.00	0.01	0.24	13.9.22 11:42
17	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-3.9	8.9	30.3	0.00	0.01	0.26	13.9.22 11:38
18	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-8.9	8.7	30.2	0.00	0.01	0.53	13.9.22 11:32
19	Grass	grass	-2.8	8.1	26.3	0.02	0.00	1.66	15.9.22 9:31
20	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-6.2	8.4	26.6	0.34	0.02	0.51	15.9.22 9:40
21	Grass	grass	-71.8	6.8	31.8	0.00	0.06	4.49	13.9.22 13:40
22	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-30.5	8.6	32.0	0.00	0.08	1.01	13.9.22 13:49
23	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-128.8	8.0	32.1	0.00	0.08	0.30	13.9.22 13:54
24	Field	sunflower (2,0 m), weed	-2.6	9.1	32.5	0.00	0.11	0.37	13.9.22 14:04
25	Field	sunflower (2,0 m)	-99.0	7.6	32.5	0.00	0.06	2.17	13.9.22 14:12
26	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-4.4	9.0	30.6	0.00	0.02	0.19	13.9.22 15:26
27	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-34.7	9.0	30.8	0.00	0.01	0.36	13.9.22 15:19
28	Grove	grove	-2.6	9.0	30.7	0.00	0.01	0.52	13.9.22 15:06
29	Field	sunflower (2 m)	-18.3	8.5	30.7	0.00	0.02	1.39	13.9.22 14:54
30	Field	sunflower (2 m)	-25.1	8.5	31.9	0.00	0.05	1.10	13.9.22 14:33
31	Field	sunflower (2 m)	-3.4	9.1	31.7	0.00	0.06	0.43	13.9.22 14:26
32	Field	sunflower (2 m)	-2.9	9.0	32.0	0.00	0.13	0.55	13.9.22 14:19
33	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-9.3	8.9	30.6	0.00	0.01	0.48	13.9.22 15:32
34	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-2.4	9.0	30.5	0.02	0.01	0.35	13.9.22 15:37
35	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-2.0	9.0	30.5	0.00	0.00	0.19	13.9.22 15:44
36	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-15.5	8.8	30.4	0.00	0.01	0.51	13.9.22 15:49
37	Field	sunflower (2 m)	-4.5	8.7	30.3	0.00	0.00	1.11	13.9.22 16:03
38	Grove	grove	-2.0	8.6	25.3	0.00	0.00	0.32	14.9.22 8:57
39	Grove	grove	-10.1	8.4	25.2	0.00	0.00	0.72	14.9.22 9:13
40	Field	ploughed field	-2.6	8.4	23.0	0.00	0.00	0.48	14.9.22 10:01
41	Field	ploughed field	-1.7	8.4	23.3	0.00	0.00	0.26	14.9.22 9:56
42	Field	ploughed field	-8.3	8.4	23.6	0.00	0.00	0.25	14.9.22 9:49
43	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-4.7	8.4	23.9	0.00	0.00	0.35	14.9.22 9:43
44	Grove	grove	-4.1	8.4	24.2	0.00	0.00	0.34	14.9.22 9:36
45	Grass	grass	-3.3	8.2	24.6	0.00	0.00	1.07	14.9.22 9:32

46	Field	harvested sunflower field	-10.7	8.4	24.8	0.00	0.00	0.53	14.9.22 9:19
47	Field	ploughed corn fld.	-7.4	8.4	23.2	0.09	0.00	0.18	14.9.22 10:08
48	Field	ploughed corn fld.	-3.4	8.3	23.1	0.00	0.00	0.38	14.9.22 10:20
49	Field	ploughed field	-4.9	8.4	22.6	0.00	0.00	0.30	14.9.22 10:27
50	Field	ploughed field	-7.6	8.3	22.0	0.00	0.00	0.37	14.9.22 10:47
51	Field	harvested sunflower field	-8.8	8.4	20.7	0.00	0.00	0.15	14.9.22 12:18
52	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-15.1	8.3	20.9	0.00	0.00	0.27	14.9.22 12:26
53	Field	harvested sunflower field	-6.9	8.3	20.9	0.00	0.00	0.15	14.9.22 12:33
54	Field	ploughed field	-7.7	8.3	22.0	0.33	0.01	0.34	14.9.22 13:30
55	Field	ploughed sunflower field	-16.3	8.0	22.3	0.02	0.00	0.98	14.9.22 13:17
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-2.5	8.4	22.4	0.40	0.01	0.21	14.9.22 13:08
57	Field	harvested sunflower field	-1.6	8.3	22.2	0.00	0.00	0.60	14.9.22 13:00
58	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-4.2	8.3	22.1	0.00	0.00	0.39	14.9.22 12:55
59	Field	ploughed wheat fld.	-15.4	8.3	22.0	0.00	0.00	0.22	14.9.22 12:48
60	Field	ploughed field	-5.2	8.4	21.5	0.46	0.02	0.20	14.9.22 13:37
61	Field	ploughed field	-9.1	8.3	21.3	0.04	0.00	0.28	14.9.22 13:43
62	Field	corn (2 m)	-3.2	8.0	24.5	0.41	0.03	1.70	15.9.22 11:04
63	Field	winter cereal ?	-26.8	7.8	25.1	0.38	0.03	0.96	15.9.22 10:55
64	Field	winter cereal ?	-3.4	8.2	24.8	0.40	0.02	0.85	15.9.22 10:47
65	Field	winter cereal ?	-33.7	8.1	26.4	0.33	0.02	0.67	15.9.22 10:02
66	Field	winter cereal ?	-8.0	8.3	26.0	0.38	0.02	0.77	15.9.22 10:10
67	Field	ploughed field	-22.2	8.0	25.9	0.34	0.02	1.50	15.9.22 10:20
68	Field	corn (2 m)	-4.8	8.3	25.3	0.42	0.03	0.69	15.9.22 10:29
101	Grass	grass (unmown)	-4.4	6.8	25.3	0.00	0.00	6.42	9.9.22 8:41
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-18.1	7.7	25.3	0.00	0.00	3.33	9.9.22 8:51
103	Field	ploughed field	-36.0	8.0	24.7	0.00	0.01	1.51	9.9.22 9:07
104	Field	ploughed field	-133.3	7.2	24.2	0.00	0.02	1.39	9.9.22 9:22
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-110.2	4.6	23.4	0.02	0.01	6.31	9.9.22 9:35
106	Field	ploughed field	-120.0	7.6	22.7	0.07	0.02	0.98	9.9.22 9:48
107	Field	ploughed field	-2.8	8.1	22.6	0.01	0.00	2.21	9.9.22 10:01
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-16.1	7.6	22.5	0.01	0.00	3.24	9.9.22 10:07
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-5.4	8.0	22.7	0.01	0.02	2.28	9.9.22 10:16
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-59.4	7.7	22.7	0.02	0.02	1.65	9.9.22 10:26
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-158.3	7.2	23.6	0.00	0.05	1.04	9.9.22 10:46
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.8	8.1	23.7	0.00	0.04	2.19	9.9.22 10:55
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-58.3	7.5	23.7	0.00	0.05	2.06	9.9.22 11:07
114	Grove	orchard	-56.4	7.8	24.6	0.00	0.07	1.45	9.9.22 11:26
115	Grass	grass	-29.2	7.5	25.7	0.00	0.07	2.60	9.9.22 11:54
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-113.1	7.3	26.4	0.00	0.08	1.59	9.9.22 12:02
117	Field	ploughed field	-135.6	7.7	26.6	0.00	0.11	0.14	9.9.22 12:10
118	Field	harvested sunflower field	-10.0	8.4	27.1	0.00	0.09	1.23	9.9.22 12:22
119	Grove	grove	-11.1	8.6	27.7	0.00	0.11	0.44	9.9.22 12:39
120	Field	weeds	-2.1	8.5	29.0	0.00	0.10	1.49	9.9.22 12:56
121	Grass	grass	-6.5	8.8	30.5	0.00	0.13	0.88	9.9.22 14:18
122	Grove	grove	-1.2	8.3	30.7	0.00	0.13	2.44	9.9.22 14:55
123	Grass	grass (mown)	-51.0	7.6	30.6	0.00	0.14	2.64	9.9.22 14:41
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-12.4	8.9	30.5	0.00	0.15	0.18	9.9.22 14:29
125	Grove	grove	-126.6	7.5	24.6	0.00	0.04	0.69	13.9.22 9:20
126	Grass	grass (mown)	-3.0	8.4	24.7	0.00	0.06	0.56	13.9.22 9:31
127	Field	ploughed field	-19.9	8.4	24.9	0.00	0.05	0.34	13.9.22 9:43

Attachment 6: 6th periodical monitoring campaign: winter 2022-2023

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	ploughed field	-73.2	19.8	17.8	0.00	0.00	0.13	14.2.23 9:16
2	Field	no vegetation	-124.1	18.8	17.1	0.00	0.00	0.06	14.2.23 9:23
3	Field	ploughed field	-116.6	19.1	14.7	0.00	0.00	0.08	14.2.23 9:49
4	Field	ploughed field	-9.6	20.8	15.2	0.00	0.00	0.08	14.2.23 9:42
5	Field	ploughed field	-2.1	20.4	15.8	0.00	0.00	0.44	14.2.23 9:37
6	Field	ploughed field	-3.1	21.1	16.3	0.00	0.00	0.07	14.2.23 9:31
7	Field	ploughed field	-4.3	21.1	14.2	0.00	0.00	0.06	14.2.23 9:56
8	Field	ploughed field	-2.2	21.1	13.8	0.00	0.00	0.07	14.2.23 10:04
9	Field	ploughed field	-165.5	19.3	13.5	0.00	0.00	0.05	14.2.23 10:10
10	Field	ploughed field	-2.0	21.1	13.3	0.00	0.00	0.06	14.2.23 10:15
11	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-11.0	20.8	13.0	0.00	0.00	0.24	14.2.23 10:19
12	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-2.9	21.2	12.7	0.00	0.00	0.05	14.2.23 10:25
13	Field	ploughed field	-83.9	20.2	12.1	0.00	0.00	0.18	14.2.23 10:58
14	Grass	grass	-121.1	18.9	12.2	0.00	0.00	0.08	14.2.23 10:54
15	Field	ploughed field	-2.6	21.1	12.4	0.00	0.00	0.08	14.2.23 10:49
16	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-47.0	20.1	12.4	0.00	0.00	0.18	14.2.23 10:45
17	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-7.6	20.9	12.5	0.00	0.00	0.06	14.2.23 10:37
18	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-31.0	20.4	12.6	0.00	0.00	0.19	14.2.23 10:30
19	Grass	grass	-3.1	21.3	10.1	0.00	0.00	0.35	14.2.23 13:21
20	Field	ploughed field	-2.3	21.3	10.3	0.00	0.00	0.19	14.2.23 13:27
21	Grass	grass	-14.5	20.8	12.1	0.00	0.00	0.08	14.2.23 11:08
22	Field	ploughed field	-4.3	21.0	12.1	0.08	0.00	0.05	14.2.23 11:13
23	Field	ploughed field	-26.4	20.3	12.3	0.11	0.00	0.15	14.2.23 11:23
24	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-51.7	19.8	12.3	0.00	0.00	0.27	14.2.23 11:31
25	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-1.5	20.9	12.2	0.13	0.00	0.20	14.2.23 11:39
26	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-2.1	21.2	10.9	0.00	0.00	0.11	14.2.23 13:40
27	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-175.0	19.0	10.6	0.00	0.00	0.17	14.2.23 13:34
28	Grove	grove	-69.1	19.6	11.4	0.00	0.00	0.31	14.2.23 12:06
29	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-4.7	20.1	11.6	0.00	0.00	1.07	14.2.23 11:58
30	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-3.9	20.9	11.8	0.00	0.00	0.17	14.2.23 11:54
31	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-6.4	20.9	12.0	0.00	0.00	0.06	14.2.23 11:49
32	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-25.5	20.5	12.0	0.12	0.00	0.05	14.2.23 11:45
33	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-24.7	20.9	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.06	14.2.23 13:50
34	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-24.4	20.7	10.8	0.00	0.00	0.21	14.2.23 13:55
35	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-4.2	21.1	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.09	14.2.23 14:00
36	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-17.4	20.9	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.16	14.2.23 14:04
37	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-4.6	21.2	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.05	14.2.23 14:10
38	Grove	grove	-50.4	20.7	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.10	14.2.23 14:17
39	Grove	grove	-97.8	19.2	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.22	14.2.23 14:25
40	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-136.7	18.9	11.5	0.00	0.00	0.15	14.2.23 15:09
41	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-4.1	20.8	11.8	0.00	0.00	0.17	14.2.23 15:00
42	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.2	20.7	11.6	0.00	0.00	0.43	14.2.23 14:54
43	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-3.0	20.9	11.4	0.00	0.00	0.10	14.2.23 14:50
44	Grove	grove	-42.3	20.2	11.1	0.00	0.00	0.16	14.2.23 14:42

45	Grass	grass	-11.9	20.8	10.9	0.00	0.00	0.24	14.2.23 14:37
46	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-9.0	20.8	10.7	0.00	0.00	0.07	14.2.23 14:32
47	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-5.9	20.8	11.5	0.00	0.00	0.15	14.2.23 15:14
48	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.1	21.1	16.5	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 9:58
49	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-3.4	20.8	15.8	0.00	0.00	0.07	15.2.23 10:04
50	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-120.2	18.0	15.4	0.00	0.00	0.52	15.2.23 10:08
51	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.8	20.8	15.0	0.00	0.00	0.07	15.2.23 10:12
52	Field	ploughed field	-1.7	20.8	14.6	0.00	0.00	0.08	15.2.23 10:16
53	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-1.8	20.8	14.2	0.00	0.00	0.14	15.2.23 10:21
54	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-3.9	20.9	12.2	0.00	0.00	0.05	15.2.23 10:47
55	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.6	20.9	12.5	0.00	0.00	0.05	15.2.23 10:43
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-2.1	20.8	12.8	0.00	0.00	0.22	15.2.23 10:38
57	Field	uncultivated field, weeds	-5.0	20.8	13.1	0.00	0.00	0.05	15.2.23 10:34
58	Field	ploughed field	-3.9	20.8	13.5	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 10:29
59	Field	ploughed field	-1.6	20.8	13.8	0.00	0.00	0.07	15.2.23 10:25
60	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-3.1	20.9	12.0	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 10:52
61	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-73.0	19.5	11.8	0.00	0.00	0.12	15.2.23 10:57
62	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.1	20.9	11.7	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 11:01
63	Field	ploughed field	-2.9	20.9	11.6	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 11:06
64	Field	ploughed field	-60.2	19.9	11.4	0.00	0.00	0.07	15.2.23 11:10
65	Field	ploughed field	-2.9	21.0	10.8	0.00	0.00	0.05	15.2.23 11:29
66	Field	ploughed field	-2.0	20.9	11.1	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 11:24
67	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.7	20.9	11.2	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 11:20
68	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.7	20.6	11.2	0.00	0.00	0.44	15.2.23 11:15
101	Grass	grass (unmown)	-4.0	19.9	19.2	0.00	0.00	1.25	15.2.23 9:21
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-15.5	20.1	19.0	0.00	0.00	0.93	15.2.23 9:31
103	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-3.7	18.0	18.7	0.00	0.00	1.52	15.2.23 9:36
104	Field	field, weeds	-4.8	21.3	12.1	0.00	0.00	0.12	15.2.23 12:51
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-11.4	20.6	12.4	0.00	0.00	0.55	15.2.23 13:18
106	Field	ploughed field	-2.6	20.1	12.3	0.00	0.00	1.30	15.2.23 13:03
107	Field	field	-12.7	20.8	12.0	0.00	0.00	0.14	15.2.23 12:40
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-2.7	19.8	11.8	0.00	0.00	1.07	15.2.23 12:33
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-1.9	20.9	11.3	0.00	0.00	0.51	15.2.23 12:26
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-91.4	19.3	12.4	0.00	0.00	0.08	15.2.23 13:53
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-4.0	21.0	12.4	0.00	0.00	0.13	15.2.23 13:45
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-59.1	20.1	12.5	0.00	0.00	0.18	15.2.23 13:39
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-17.3	21.0	12.3	0.00	0.00	0.14	15.2.23 13:32
114	Grove	orchard	-21.7	20.5	12.2	0.00	0.00	0.32	15.2.23 14:05
115	Grass	grass, weeds	-148.5	17.4	12.6	0.00	0.00	0.56	15.2.23 14:15
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-5.8	20.5	12.7	0.00	0.00	0.25	15.2.23 14:20
117	Field	winter cereal (10 cm)	-214.6	19.1	12.9	0.00	0.00	0.04	15.2.23 14:29
118	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-10.7	20.9	11.5	0.00	0.00	0.06	15.2.23 14:45
119	Grove	grove	-2.5	20.0	12.4	0.00	0.00	0.58	16.2.22 13:55
120	Field	weeds	-2.1	20.1	11.1	0.00	0.00	0.69	16.2.23 11:10
121	Grass	grass	-2.4	20.4	12.0	0.00	0.00	0.44	16.2.23 10:46
122	Grove	grove	-2.2	20.3	10.1	0.00	0.00	1.06	15.2.23 15:01
123	Grass	grass (mown)	-201.6	16.6	17.0	0.00	0.00	0.45	16.2.23 9:34
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-67.3	19.6	16.9	0.00	0.00	0.07	16.2.23 9:44
125	Grove	grove	-4.4	20.3	15.4	0.00	0.00	0.29	16.2.23 10:06
126	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.4	20.1	13.7	0.00	0.00	0.70	16.2.23 10:18
127	Field	winter cereal (5 cm)	-198.9	16.5	12.9	0.00	0.00	0.09	16.2.23 10:28

Attachment 7: 7th periodical monitoring campaign: spring 2023

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	sunflower (20 cm)	-21.2	19.2	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.39	24.5.23 10:26
2	Field	no vegetation	-275.3	16.4	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.32	24.5.23 10:32
3	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-9.2	19.2	26.2	0.00	0.00	0.35	24.5.23 10:53
4	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-45.1	18.3	26.3	0.00	0.00	0.33	24.5.23 10:49
5	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-9.1	17.0	26.2	0.00	0.00	1.24	24.5.23 10:44
6	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-137.8	14.5	26.2	0.00	0.00	0.74	24.5.23 10:40
7	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-432.9	14.6	26.3	0.00	0.00	0.51	24.5.23 10:58
8	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-149.0	16.1	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.42	24.5.23 11:03
9	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-400.3	17.7	25.7	0.00	0.00	0.64	24.5.23 11:08
10	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-28.1	18.3	25.3	0.00	0.00	0.50	24.5.23 11:16
11	Field	cereal (1 m)	-58.3	17.3	24.8	0.00	0.00	0.91	24.5.23 11:22
12	Field	cereal (1 m)	-30.4	17.2	24.7	0.00	0.00	1.41	24.5.23 11:26
13	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-278.4	15.0	25.4	0.00	0.00	0.26	25.5.23 12:25
14	Grass	grass (mown)	-55.8	17.1	24.3	0.00	0.00	1.02	24.5.23 11:56
15	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-80.0	17.3	24.2	0.00	0.00	0.36	24.5.23 11:51
16	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-141.1	15.5	24.2	0.00	0.00	1.27	24.5.23 11:44
17	Field	cereal (1 m)	-30.0	18.0	24.2	0.00	0.00	0.75	24.5.23 11:38
18	Field	cereal (1 m)	-38.5	15.6	24.5	0.00	0.00	2.25	24.5.23 11:31
19	Grass	grass (mown)	-5.5	16.6	26.1	0.00	0.00	2.73	24.5.23 12:47
20	Field	cereal (50 cm), weeds	-28.9	17.9	26.2	0.00	0.00	0.84	24.5.23 12:53
21	Grass	grass	-119.4	14.6	26.6	0.00	0.00	2.49	24.5.23 13:00
22	Field	sunflower (10 cm)	-99.5	17.2	26.8	0.00	0.00	0.15	24.5.23 13:07
23	Field	cereal (50 cm), weeds	-142.5	16.3	27.3	0.03	0.00	0.09	24.5.23 13:14
24	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-58.8	17.0	28.0	0.00	0.00	0.92	24.5.23 13:22
25	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-1.8	18.5	28.2	0.00	0.00	0.84	24.5.23 13:32
26	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-13.0	18.5	27.5	0.00	0.00	0.84	24.5.23 14:20
27	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-9.6	18.4	27.6	0.00	0.00	1.03	24.5.23 14:15
28	Grove	grove	-2.9	17.3	28.0	0.00	0.00	1.96	24.5.23 14:06
29	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-5.4	15.8	28.2	0.00	0.00	3.56	24.5.23 13:59
30	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-32.1	17.6	28.4	0.00	0.00	1.20	24.5.23 13:52
31	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-108.6	16.5	28.5	0.00	0.00	0.82	24.5.23 13:46
32	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-21.2	18.2	28.2	0.00	0.00	0.74	24.5.23 13:39
33	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-2.4	18.2	28.0	0.00	0.00	1.47	24.5.23 14:30
34	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-8.0	18.7	28.2	0.00	0.00	0.68	24.5.23 14:35
35	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-7.6	18.2	28.2	0.00	0.00	1.20	24.5.23 14:42
36	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-5.5	18.1	28.0	0.00	0.00	1.12	24.5.23 14:49
37	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-27.5	18.4	28.1	0.00	0.00	0.60	24.5.23 14:57
38	Grove	grove	-4.8	17.7	28.2	0.00	0.00	1.32	24.5.23 15:03
39	Grove	grove	-21.4	14.9	28.1	0.00	0.00	2.72	24.5.23 15:12
40	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-14.5	18.1	27.5	0.00	0.00	0.77	24.5.23 15:57
41	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-18.8	18.2	28.0	0.00	0.00	0.95	24.5.23 15:49
42	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-23.1	18.0	28.4	0.00	0.00	0.90	24.5.23 15:42
43	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-3.0	18.5	28.6	0.00	0.00	0.85	24.5.23 15:35
44	Grove	grove	-3.9	17.7	28.5	0.00	0.00	1.68	24.5.23 15:29
45	Grass	grass (unmown)	-5.6	17.7	28.2	0.00	0.00	1.35	24.5.23 15:23
46	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-64.7	16.8	28.0	0.00	0.00	0.74	24.5.23 15:19
47	Field	ploughed field	-166.8	15.4	27.3	0.00	0.00	0.55	24.5.23 16:03
48	Field	ploughed field	-3.5	18.4	27.3	0.00	0.00	0.87	24.5.23 16:10
49	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-4.9	17.9	27.3	0.00	0.00	1.72	24.5.23 16:16
50	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-3.7	18.2	27.0	0.00	0.00	1.59	24.5.23 16:21
51	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-11.6	18.6	26.1	0.00	0.00	1.18	25.5.23 10:48
52	Field	corn (10 cm)	-39.1	17.6	26.2	0.00	0.00	0.88	25.5.23 10:54
53	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-36.2	17.5	26.3	0.00	0.00	1.85	25.5.23 11:00
54	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-14.1	14.9	24.5	0.00	0.00	1.24	25.5.23 12:40

55	Field	corn (10 cm)	-29.6	17.4	26.3	0.00	0.00	1.79	25.5.23 11:25
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-2.9	18.4	26.4	0.00	0.00	1.64	25.5.23 11:22
57	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-50.4	17.8	26.5	0.00	0.00	1.24	25.5.23 11:16
58	Field	corn (10 cm)	-4.6	18.9	26.5	0.00	0.00	0.50	25.5.23 11:11
59	Field	corn (10 cm)	-17.0	17.5	26.4	0.00	0.00	0.72	25.5.23 11:06
60	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-4.8	18.2	24.9	0.00	0.00	1.43	25.5.23 12:45
61	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-17.5	18.6	27.4	0.00	0.00	1.27	25.5.23 12:52
62	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-9.6	17.6	28.3	0.00	0.00	4.38	25.5.23 12:58
63	Field	corn (10 cm)	-3.8	17.5	29.1	0.00	0.00	1.91	25.5.23 13:04
64	Field	corn (10 cm)	-21.0	16.6	29.4	0.00	0.00	2.06	25.5.23 13:09
65	Field	corn (10 cm)	-4.7	17.4	30.0	0.00	0.00	0.68	25.5.23 13:34
66	Field	corn (10 cm)	-10.9	18.4	30.0	0.00	0.00	0.65	25.5.23 13:30
67	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-122.4	17.8	29.9	0.00	0.00	0.85	25.5.23 13:24
68	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-2.9	16.6	29.7	0.00	0.00	1.53	25.5.23 13:18
101	Grass	grass (mown)	-24.6	18.4	25.2	0.00	0.00	0.96	23.5.23 11:04
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-4.0	17.4	25.8	0.00	0.00	2.47	23.5.23 11:10
103	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-15.4	19.2	26.8	0.00	0.00	0.11	23.5.23 11:18
104	Field	field, weeds	-5.1	18.4	28.2	0.00	0.00	1.30	23.5.23 11:29
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-3.5	16.8	31.3	0.00	0.00	2.77	23.5.23 11:51
106	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-172.7	15.6	30.7	0.00	0.00	0.33	23.5.23 11:45
107	Field	wheat (40 cm)	-3.7	17.6	31.7	0.00	0.00	1.49	23.5.23 13:20
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-11.0	16.7	31.4	0.00	0.00	2.14	23.5.23 13:12
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-4.9	16.6	31.3	0.00	0.00	2.33	23.5.23 13:06
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-33.2	14.1	32.1	0.00	0.00	3.87	23.5.23 13:32
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-6.4	16.8	31.6	0.00	0.00	2.47	23.5.23 12:22
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-19.4	17.5	31.6	0.00	0.00	1.47	23.5.23 12:12
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-20.3	14.9	31.6	0.00	0.00	2.68	23.5.23 12:05
114	Grove	orchard	-7.5	17.2	31.5	0.00	0.00	2.04	23.5.23 11:57
115	Grass	grass, weeds	-85.5	14.8	32.7	0.00	0.00	1.65	23.5.23 13:54
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-3.8	17.2	32.7	0.00	0.00	1.61	23.5.23 13:59
117	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-9.5	17.7	32.8	0.00	0.00	0.82	23.5.23 14:04
118	Field	cereal (30 cm)	-310.7	14.9	25.6	0.01	0.00	0.46	25.5.23 10:25
119	Grove	grove	-46.4	14.9	25.9	0.00	0.00	2.77	25.5.23 10:08
120	Field	weeds	-15.5	18.3	25.9	0.00	0.00	1.35	25.5.23 9:58
121	Grass	grass (mown)	-16.0	16.9	29.3	0.00	0.00	1.82	23.5.23 15:06
122	Grove	grove	-7.9	16.2	32.6	0.00	0.00	2.88	23.5.23 14:12
123	Grass	grass (mown)	-16.1	14.3	32.0	0.00	0.00	5.61	23.5.23 14:22
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-5.1	17.3	31.6	0.00	0.00	1.50	23.5.23 14:28
125	Grove	grove	-43.4	15.0	30.5	0.00	0.00	2.59	23.5.23 14:43
126	Grass	grass (mown)	-20.0	15.6	30.3	0.00	0.00	2.90	23.5.23 14:49
127	Field	cereal (50 cm)	-8.6	14.5	29.6	0.00	0.00	4.00	23.5.23 14:59

Attachment 8: 8th periodical monitoring campaign: summer-autumn 2023

Point	Land use	Vegetation	Sample P (hPa)	O ₂ (%)	T (°C)	CH ₄ av. (%)	TP av. (%)	CO ₂ av. (%)	Date (d.m.yy h:mm)
1	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-12.6	17.7	25.9	0.00	0.00	2.27	2.10.23 9:48
2	Field	no vegetation	-101.5	16.4	26.0	0.04	0.01	1.01	2.10.23 9:54
3	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-10.1	18.7	27.6	0.02	0.00	0.37	2.10.23 10:20
4	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-2.8	18.5	27.4	0.00	0.00	1.41	2.10.23 10:14
5	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-19.9	18.4	27.1	0.03	0.02	0.57	2.10.23 10:06
6	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-155.4	16.4	26.6	0.00	0.00	1.35	2.10.23 10:01
7	Field	ploughed (sunflower) field	-2.1	18.6	28.2	0.03	0.01	0.30	2.10.23 10:32
8	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-2.0	18.6	28.5	0.04	0.01	0.39	2.10.23 10:39
9	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-40.4	17.7	28.6	0.00	0.00	0.99	2.10.23 10:44
10	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-29.5	17.8	29.3	0.00	0.00	1.11	2.10.23 10:53
11	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-23.6	17.7	29.4	0.00	0.00	1.35	2.10.23 10:57
12	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-43.0	17.9	29.7	0.05	0.01	0.41	2.10.23 11:02
13	Field	sunflower (2 m)	-42.1	16.5	30.0	0.00	0.00	3.43	2.10.23 11:39
14	Grass	grass (mown)	-5.7	17.8	30.5	0.00	0.00	1.65	2.10.23 11:31
15	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-62.4	17.3	30.4	0.00	0.00	0.63	2.10.23 11:24
16	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-13.7	18.2	30.2	0.00	0.00	0.58	2.10.23 11:17
17	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-32.4	17.4	30.1	0.00	0.00	1.83	2.10.23 11:12
18	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-3.7	17.7	30.0	0.00	0.00	2.38	2.10.23 11:07
19	Grass	grass (mown)	-7.1	18.5	27.5	0.00	0.00	2.49	3.10.23 15:43
20	Field	clover, weeds	-2.6	18.8	27.6	0.00	0.00	2.08	3.10.23 15:48
21	Grass	grass	-21.1	17.7	30.2	0.00	0.00	1.57	2.10.23 12:31
22	Field	sunflower (1,5 m)	-72.6	13.9	30.8	0.00	0.00	3.80	2.10.23 12:39
23	Field	ploughed field	-171.0	16.5	31.1	0.02	0.00	0.74	2.10.23 12:44
24	Field	ploughed field	-7.5	18.2	31.5	0.00	0.00	0.72	2.10.23 12:50
25	Field	ploughed field	-46.9	17.6	31.7	0.03	0.00	0.47	2.10.23 12:54
26	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-2.9	18.1	31.6	0.00	0.00	0.65	2.10.23 13:44
27	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-7.2	17.9	31.6	0.00	0.00	0.64	2.10.23 13:40
28	Grove	grove	-4.3	18.1	31.9	0.00	0.00	0.55	2.10.23 13:30
29	Field	ploughed field	-44.7	16.8	32.3	0.00	0.00	1.88	2.10.23 13:21
30	Field	ploughed field	-85.1	16.5	32.4	0.00	0.00	1.64	2.10.23 13:13
31	Field	ploughed field	-25.4	17.7	32.4	0.00	0.00	1.10	2.10.23 13:09
32	Field	ploughed field	-4.5	18.3	32.1	0.01	0.00	0.35	2.10.23 13:03
33	Field	ploughed field	-27.1	17.6	31.5	0.00	0.00	0.80	2.10.23 13:54
34	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-6.9	17.5	31.6	0.00	0.00	1.60	2.10.23 13:59
35	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-19.2	15.7	31.6	0.05	0.01	1.53	2.10.23 14:03
36	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-55.4	16.6	31.8	0.00	0.00	1.91	2.10.23 14:12
37	Field	ploughed field	-77.0	16.6	31.8	0.00	0.00	1.05	2.10.23 14:21
38	Grove	grove	-10.1	17.9	32.3	0.03	0.00	0.47	2.10.23 14:28
39	Grove	grove	-9.2	15.7	32.5	0.00	0.00	6.28	2.10.23 14:39
40	Field	ploughed field	-18.7	18.3	26.4	0.00	0.00	0.59	3.10.23 15:23
41	Field	ploughed field	-23.4	17.6	31.9	0.00	0.00	0.71	2.10.23 15:17
42	Field	ploughed field	-4.0	17.9	32.0	0.05	0.00	0.68	2.10.23 15:12
43	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-74.6	17.3	32.2	0.01	0.00	0.38	2.10.23 15:05
44	Grove	grove	-12.3	17.7	32.3	0.00	0.00	0.38	2.10.23 15:00
45	Grass	grass (unmown)	-1.7	17.3	32.5	0.00	0.00	1.43	2.10.23 14:53
46	Field	ploughed field	-165.8	14.0	32.5	0.00	0.00	3.02	2.10.23 14:47
47	Field	ploughed field	-4.3	18.8	26.2	0.00	0.00	0.39	3.10.23 9:03

48	Field	ploughed field	-92.4	17.1	26.0	0.00	0.00	1.22	3.10.23 9:09
49	Field	ploughed field	-62.9	17.4	26.0	0.04	0.01	1.13	3.10.23 9:15
50	Field	ploughed field	-33.2	18.3	25.9	0.00	0.00	0.62	3.10.23 9:22
51	Field	ploughed field, cereal remains	-87.4	17.2	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.79	3.10.23 9:29
52	Field	corn (1,5 m)	-3.1	18.5	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.53	3.10.23 9:33
53	Field	ploughed field, cereal remains	-6.8	18.4	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.64	3.10.23 9:38
54	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-60.7	17.6	26.5	0.00	0.00	0.51	3.10.23 10:17
55	Field	ploughed field, corn remains	-3.1	18.4	26.5	0.00	0.00	1.10	3.10.23 10:10
56	Grass	grass / weeds	-3.6	18.5	26.4	0.00	0.00	0.76	3.10.23 10:06
57	Field	field / weeds	-3.7	18.5	26.3	0.02	0.00	0.63	3.10.23 9:59
58	Field	corn (2 m)	-6.4	18.6	26.3	0.00	0.00	0.72	3.10.23 9:53
59	Field	corn (2 m)	-1.6	18.5	26.0	0.00	0.00	0.66	3.10.23 9:46
60	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-1.5	18.6	26.5	0.00	0.00	0.61	3.10.23 10:24
61	Field	ploughed field, winter cereal (5 cm)	-195.6	18.1	26.8	0.00	0.00	1.16	3.10.23 10:31
62	Field	ploughed field	-12.4	18.2	26.8	0.00	0.00	1.28	3.10.23 10:35
63	Field	corn (2 m)	-1.7	18.5	27.2	0.00	0.00	0.51	3.10.23 10:41
64	Field	corn (2 m)	-1.5	18.7	27.5	0.00	0.00	0.58	3.10.23 10:47
65	Field	corn (2 m)	-3.1	18.3	28.2	0.00	0.00	1.95	3.10.23 11:20
66	Field	corn (2 m)	-12.9	18.4	28.3	0.00	0.00	0.49	3.10.23 11:13
67	Field	ploughed field	-41.4	16.6	28.2	0.00	0.00	4.52	3.10.23 11:03
68	Field	ploughed field	-93.8	16.6	28.1	0.00	0.00	2.14	3.10.23 10:58
101	Grass	grass (mown)	-26.9	17.0	28.3	0.00	0.00	3.28	3.10.23 12:00
102	Grass	grass (unmown)	-14.2	18.6	28.6	0.00	0.00	2.42	3.10.23 12:10
103	Field	ploughed field, wheat remains	-4.9	18.5	30.3	0.13	0.03	1.63	3.10.23 12:29
104	Field	ploughed field	-2.1	18.8	30.4	0.02	0.00	1.02	3.10.23 12:42
105	Grass	grass (unmown)	-2.3	18.1	30.5	0.12	0.01	2.06	3.10.23 13:01
106	Field	ploughed field	-2.0	17.4	30.4	0.00	0.00	4.09	3.10.23 12:51
107	Field	ploughed field	-2.2	18.6	30.7	0.09	0.01	1.19	3.10.23 13:13
108	Grass	grass (unmown)	-3.3	17.9	31.4	0.12	0.02	1.43	3.10.23 13:26
109	Grass	grass (mown)	-1.6	19.1	26.3	0.08	0.02	1.59	3.10.23 13:32
110	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.8	18.9	26.8	0.00	0.00	1.86	4.10.23 11:07
111	Grass	grass (unmown)	-1.4	18.8	26.6	0.00	0.00	2.15	4.10.23 11:00
112	Grass	grass (mown)	-22.8	19.2	27.6	0.00	0.00	1.12	4.10.23 11:21
113	Grass	grass (mown)	-8.1	19.3	27.6	0.00	0.00	1.52	4.10.23 11:29
114	Grove	orchard	-32.3	18.4	27.3	0.01	0.00	1.90	4.10.23 11:41
115	Grass	grass, weeds	-2.9	18.5	27.3	0.00	0.00	3.53	4.10.23 11:48
116	Grass	grass (unmown)	-87.2	17.5	27.6	0.00	0.00	0.98	4.10.23 11:58
117	Field	ploughed field	-68.2	18.1	27.8	0.05	0.00	0.65	4.10.23 12:06
118	Field	ploughed field	-3.4	19.5	27.9	0.06	0.01	0.82	4.10.23 12:18
119	Grove	grove	-1.5	19.1	26.8	0.04	0.00	0.90	4.10.23 14:42
120	Field	ploughed field	-8.3	18.9	27.0	0.10	0.01	1.99	4.10.23 15:03
121	Grass	grass (mown)	-60.1	15.2	28.2	0.00	0.00	5.33	4.10.23 13:08
122	Grove	grove	-1.5	17.9	26.9	0.00	0.00	2.78	4.10.23 14:28
123	Grass	grass (mown)	-7.7	16.1	27.1	0.00	0.00	5.72	4.10.23 14:17
124	Grass	grass (unmown)	-16.8	17.5	27.7	0.00	0.00	4.36	4.10.23 13:59
125	Grove	grove	-41.1	18.4	27.7	0.00	0.00	1.29	4.10.23 13:44
126	Grass	grass (mown)	-2.2	19.0	28.2	0.00	0.00	0.97	4.10.23 13:37
127	Field	ploughed field	-63.0	14.6	28.2	0.00	0.00	5.40	4.10.23 13:18

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More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

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